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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASID	Address Space Identifier
CC	Confidential Computing
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CSEM	Child Sexual Exploitation Material
CNI	Container Network Interface
CVM	Confidential Virtual Machine
DGA	Data Governance Act
DL	Deep Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DRH	Data Rights Holder
EEG	Electroencephalography
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FDE	Full Disk Encryption
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
IOMMU	Input Output Memory Management Unit
SGX	Software Guard Extensions
MEG	Magnetoencephalography
ML	Machine Learning
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NPU	Neural Processing Unit

ACRONYM	MEANING
PBKDF	Password-Based Key Derivation Function
PIPL	Personal Information Protection Law
SEV	Secure Encrypted Virtualization
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TDE	Trust Domain Extension
UC	Use Cases
UI	User Interface
US	User Stories
VM	Virtual Machine

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, data is everywhere, and an important part of it is considered sensitive, for example: banking information, web browser history, health, location, political views, etc. Private data misuse can have detrimental effects on individuals, therefore the importance of safeguarding this information has become a critical concern, as can be seen on the UN Trade and Development report [\[18\]](#).

The data protection legal frameworks arise to enact such protection into the law. For example, in the European Union the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is applicable to all personal data originating from the European Union (EU), even if the processing is carried outside the EU, as per article 3.1 of the GDPR. This standard seeks to regulate the protection of data of natural persons and their free movement. According to the GDPR, anonymized data is "information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable" [\[1\]](#).

This law therefore establishes that pseudonymization is not the same as anonymization. In addition, concerning regulation in the EU, the Data Governance Act (DGA) [\[2\]](#) aims to make more data available and facilitate data exchange between sectors and EU countries. The DGA became effective as of June 23, 2022, and it is applicable as of September 2023. Finally, the AI Act [\[3\]](#) (which was approved on March 13, 2024) is the first regulation on Artificial Intelligence (AI), and it aims to mitigate the risks of this technology on the fundamental rights of EU citizens and on European security.

Regarding other regulations, the U.S. Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) [\[4\]](#), forces companies that process Protected Health Information (PHI) to implement and follow physical, network and process security measures. In China, the first data protection law is the Personal Information Protection Law (PIPL), which came into effect on 1 November 2021, and includes rules for the processing of personal sensitive information.

Cloud computing makes those problems even harder to tackle, because data can be distributed on third parties controlled infrastructure, it may also be under different legal and regulatory constraints. In this line, concerning machine and deep learning (DL) models, different distributed learning architectures such as Federated Learning (FL) [\[7\]](#) arise as the state of the art for training such models without data sharing or centralization with an external server. In addition, advanced cryptographic protocols for privacy-preserving such as Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC) [\[5\]](#) and Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [\[6\]](#) enable making computation on encrypted data.

Confidential computing is about securing data. At every moment, data should stay protected from unauthorized access: when stored (at rest), when used and also when in transit between the different places where it can reside. This problem is becoming so important that an international conference on *Open Confidential Computing* [\[9\]](#) has been organized with the major players in the computing landscape. From hardware vendors like Intel, Nvidia, AMD and ARM, to software companies like Microsoft, Google, IBM, Amazon and Suse. The Linux Foundation [\[11\]](#) also created a consortium [\[12\]](#) to help progress on the subject.

In order to promote Open Science, scientists need to have access to research data and results. Specifically, the EOSC aims to improve scientific research by facilitating the access to such data, promoting collaboration between different parties (FL and other privacy-aware distributed architectures can enter into play here). However, the data involved in different research processes may possess sensitive features or confidential information regarding identifiable individuals, for example personal data (medical, surveillance, opinions, habits, etc.).

For developing accurate machine learning and deep learning models, the need to have access to large volumes of data from different sources and fields is growing. Being able to use sensitive data for training AI data-based models is becoming more and more important to deliver better science. One of the main concerns that arises is how we can develop such models and applications when dealing with sensitive data in strict compliance with the applicable regulations in relation to the protection of the data involved.

Following the H2020 Program Guidelines on FAIR Data [\[10\]](#), which can be summarized by "*as open as possible and as closed as necessary*", Open Science has to cater with the duality of being able to interoperate with other open science participants, and at the same time keep sensitive data confidential, to safeguard privacy.

In this sense, it is essential for researchers to have a computing platform that allows them to have access to tools, services, and methodologies for the effective sharing of sensitive data, including trusted cloud-based environments for performing such computations and anonymization tools for ensuring compliance with the current legislation and preventing privacy breaches. Then, the SIESTA project aims to provide users with such a platform in order to help alleviate these problems and enable science to use confidential data safely.

The consortium is working in tight collaboration with other EOSC-related projects, especially EOSC-ENTRUST [\[14\]](#) and TITAN [\[13\]](#) which have received funding under the same call as SIESTA.

1.1. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The main goal of this deliverable is to present the elicitation of functional and non-functional requirements from the use cases (UC) and to define a first version of the SIESTA platform architecture.

This document is structured as follows:

- In this section (Section 1), we have presented the introduction and motivation for developing the SIESTA platform.
- Section 2 shows the conceptual architecture.
- Section 3 presents the outcomes of the use cases survey and their functional and non-functional requirements.
- Section 4 presents current service offering of the different infrastructure providers.
- Section 5 provides background information on some available technologies that may be used to set up the architecture.
- Section 6 depicts the platform architecture to implement.
- To end this deliverable, a final summary is provided in Section 7.

2. CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE

This chapter focuses on articulating high-level concepts, principles, and relationships within a domain of our project, primarily defined by the Use Cases in the next chapter.

The main objective of the herein proposed conceptual framework is to understand the key components, structures, and dynamics that shape a project's strategic direction and operational activities, specifically:

- Strategic Alignment.
- Abstraction and Generalization.
- Use Case Stakeholders Perspectives.
- Communication and Visualization.

The high level abstract architecture concepts presented in this section will be refined, and described in a more specific way in the following sections. For example, we will start by presenting the “*SIESTA user*”, without explicitly defining how that concept will be implemented within the platform.

We will describe some generic user stories (US) related to each subject that will help to understand what users may expect from the platform. This will later on be made more explicit in the Use Cases (UC) section and annexed documents. The Use Cases will explain their requirements with answers in a questionnaire built by WP6 and a “Personas, EPICs & User Stories” [15] following an agile methodology.

2.1. NOTATION

The SIESTA architecture notation and diagrams follow the [C4 model](https://c4model.com/)², a lightweight approach to visualize and diagram software architectures. The C4 model provides an abstraction-first approach providing guidelines to ensure that architecture documents are understandable, regardless of the chosen notation. C4 is based on a hierarchy of abstractions, each of them corresponding to a different level in the system: a **software system** is made up of one or more **containers** (applications and data stores, not to be confused with the term used for operating system level virtualization), each of which contains one or more **components**, which in turn are implemented by one or more **code elements**. In order to visualize this hierarchy, one must define a collection of **Context** (i.e. **systems interacting with each other**), **Containers**, **Components**, and **Code** diagrams.

The current deliverable and architecture document covers the following main visualizations:

- **System Landscape diagram**: This diagram provides a set of related systems and how they interact with each other, showing dependencies with external entities and the user relations.

² <https://c4model.com/>

- **System Context diagrams:** These diagrams describe how a specific system fits in the overall landscape.

Additional and more fine-grained visualizations (like container diagrams, deployment views and dynamic views) will be elaborated during the lifetime of the project and will be included in D8.1.

SIESTA strives to provide an open architecture model and the SIESTA C4 model diagrams are automatically generated using the [Structurizr Domain Specific Language \(DSL\)](#)³, with an online and open version of the updated diagrams in the following links:

- Diagrams, in a browseable and online live version: [\[LINK\]](#)⁴
- Code (DSL): <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/architecture> and in <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13347732>

While the diagrams are included in the current document, readers are encouraged to visualize them in the online and live version whenever feasible. Doing so will facilitate navigation through the various drawings and interactions.

³ <https://github.com/structurizr>

⁴ <https://structurizr.com/share/94201/c50c8b32-ebb1-4963-a4f0-51193eee0fba>

2.2. GLOBAL VIEW OF THE ENVISIONED PLATFORM

The envisioned platform is depicted from an abstract and conceptual point of view on [Figure 1](#).

[System Landscape]
Copyright: European Union, 2019. All Central European Summer Time

Figure 1. High level platform overview ⁵

On this diagram, it should be noted that the different roles (*User, Data Rights Holder, Code reviewer, Auditor*) are not exclusive from each other. For example, a Data Rights Holder (DRH) may also have an auditor role for his data, to monitor who accessed it, or for a researcher to know who used his computing results.

This high-level overview is divided into two parts to make the specific details clearer: Data Processing and Data Storage.

⁵ https://structurizr.com/workspace/94201/diagrams#system_view

2.3. SECURE COMPUTE

The SIESTA platform is detailed from the point of view of secure computing in [Figure 2](#). The different components are shown with their interactions and relations with the users and the secure storage platform subset. These relations are described by generic user stories that will be further detailed in the following sections and annexed documents.

Figure 2. High level secure compute overview⁶

2.3.1. Main user stories

The following is a list of user stories related to the secure computing side of the envisioned SIESTA platform:

- US-SC-1: As a SIESTA user, I want to be able to securely access sensitive data from the SIESTA secure storage which I have been given privileges to, in order to perform computations.
- US-SC-2: As a SIESTA user, I want to be able to manage my analysis code in a centralized code repository, so that it can be verified, used and enhanced.
- US-SC-3: As a SIESTA DRH, I want to be able to utilize trusted libraries within my analysis code, so that I will be assured data stays safe.
- US-SC-4: As a SIESTA user, I want my analysis code to be reviewed for potential security risks and vulnerabilities, so that the DRH can be assured the data stays safe.

⁶ https://structurizr.com/workspace/94201/diagrams#container_compute_view

- US-SC-5: As a SIESTA user, I want to be able to utilize a trusted Compute environment for running my analysis pipeline, so that accessing sensitive data is easily possible.
- US-SC-6: As a SIESTA user, I want to be able to get the results of my pipeline/analysis in order to publish it, so that science progress can be made.

2.2.2. Main services & functions

The envisioned platform’s secure computing services with their functions from an abstract point of view are listed below. They will be detailed in the following sections and will be refined into technical choices that will define the concrete platform that the resource providers will implement.

- **Compute environment** service provides functions
 - Trusted & confidential computing
 - Analytics workload sandboxing
 - Configuration automation
 - Secrets management

- **Code repository** service provides functions
 - Code Quality analysis (SAST, DAST)
 - Collaborative development (code, issues, documentation)
 - Best practices policy enforcement
 - Code review for confidentiality
 - Automation pipelines

- **Software mirror** (Trusted Registry) service provides functions
 - Trusted supply chain
 - Vulnerability (CVE) scanning
 - Artefact signing

- **Remote desktop** service provides functions
 - Interactive analytics and visualization
 - Running full Linux applications and scripts/workflows

2.3. SECURE STORAGE

The SIESTA platform is detailed from the point of view of secure storage in [Figure 3](#). The different components are shown with their interactions and relations with the users and the secure compute platform subset. These relations are described by generic user stories that will be further detailed in the following sections and annexed documents.

Figure 3. High level secure storage overview⁷

2.3.1. Main user stories

These are user stories related to the secure storage side of the envisioned SIESTA platform:

- US-SS-1: As a DRH, I want to be able to securely upload a sensitive data set into SIESTA secure storage, so that researchers can use it safely.
- US-SS-2: As a DRH, I want to be able to grant access to my data to specified people/groups so that they can use it for their research.
- US-SS-3: As a DRH, I want my data set to be protected from unauthorized access by another user of the SIESTA or an insider or outsider, so that privacy is not breached.
- US-SS-4: As a DRH, I want to assess who has accessed my data, so that I can ensure only authorized people accessed it.

⁷ https://structurizr.com/workspace/94201/diagrams#container_storage_view

2.3.2. Main services & functions

The envisioned platform's secure storage services with their functions from an abstract point of view are listed below. They will be detailed in the following sections and will be translated into technical choices that will define the concrete platform that the resource providers will implement.

- **Encrypted storage** service provides functions
 - Integrity : Detection of data tampering
 - Security: Advanced data protection measures

- **Data ingestion system** service provides functions
 - Data (pseudo-)anonymization
 - If data is already anonymized, check the level of anonymity
 - Metadata format validation

- **Egress** service provides functions
 - Easy results data sharing for publishing
 - Disclosure risk evaluation

- **Assisted anonymization tool** service provides functions
 - Anonymizing data when applicable according to the different techniques available in the platform (using the ANJANA Python library developed within WP10), and aiming to prevent different kinds of attacks. This will be further explained in the next chapters.

2.4. CONCLUSION

To delve further into the details of the requirements for the SIESTA platform, the next section will describe a few use cases, and some of the more specific user stories that emerge from their needs. Moreover, the functions and services solutions will be investigated in the technology scouting section.

3. USE CASES

3.1. METHODOLOGY

In order to obtain a detailed view of the needs and requirements on the platform from the different use cases, a methodology based on the use of a comprehensive questionnaire was carried out.

This questionnaire was distributed to the five use cases and subsequent interviews and meetings were arranged according to their needs, aiming to collect specific details and aspects of the scientific requirements from each use case.

To complement the questionnaire and gather more concrete and actionable items to help define the SIESTA technical platform in accordance with the use cases needs, we also gathered a “Personas, EPICs & User Stories” [\[15\]](#) document. This document is inspired by the agile methodology. It helps the use cases to define users or different kinds of stakeholders (the “Personas”) that will interact with the platform and describe the interactions they will have with it at a high level (the “EPICs”). Then those interactions will be refined in small “User Stories” (US), that are finally distilled, by the project technical team, into the final specific platform requirements.

Moreover, in order to better understand the characteristics (sizes, retention durations, confidentiality levels, etc.) of the data sets that will be used within the platform, a Data Management Plan (DMP) (deliverable D1.2) has been elaborated in parallel. This document is also useful to shape some of the platform requirements, even if only in a partial state of completeness. The WP6 & WP1 worked with the different use cases to provide the DMP documents. The DMPs are provided as direct links to the relevant entries in the ARGOS [\[16\]](#) DMP handling service, where they are officially referenced.

The data must be tagged with appropriate sensitivity levels so as to understand the security and privacy risks they convey. A table describing these sensitivity levels is located in [Annexes III](#).

Following are the different use cases summarized, with links to the additional documents containing further details, as explained above.

3.2. USE CASE 1: EPIDEMIOLOGY

This use case, managed by WP14, will use sensitive data related to population, mobility and surveillance, to enhance epidemiology research.

For example, to study how generic infectious diseases spread within populations and enable production of accurate & FAIR predictive propagation patterns models, that will help policy makers take informed decisions about containment measures at different levels (city, country, continent).

Input data is seldom updated, up to a few times per year, has low privacy/sensitivity level (already pseudonymized), but may not be legally shared back.

Most of the actual data flow will be output data handled to the platform users (researchers, policy makers, etc.). This data will be graphics, statistics, etc. The input data being aggregated statistical population data over large time spans will only change sparingly (about a few times per year).

User management is expected to be provided by the SIESTA platform. The requirements concerning computing resources are not very high. A few different user accounts, for data upload, workload launch, result retrieval. Use case is interested in resource usage.

User Interface (UI) will probably be web frontend. Computing will be done inside docker containers.

Example user story:

UC1.E01.US02
 As a researcher, I want to be able to access a graphical user interface to use some visualization tools and build my own epidemic model and exploiting the available data (agent based, age-structured, meta-population, vector borne disease model)

Use case 1 questionnaire	Annexes I - UC1
Use case 1 Personas-EPICs-User Stories document	Annexes II - UC1
Use case 1 DMP	DMP

Table 1. Important links and documents concerning use case 1.

3.3. USE CASE 2: MEDICAL IMAGING

This second use case, managed by WP15, focusses on computational research for medical data, more specifically, for human neuroimaging for which data analysis is used to understand the functioning of the brain in relation to disease, cognition, and development.

Neuroimaging is conducted in research institutes using techniques shared with hospitals, such as *Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)*, *Positron Emission Tomography (PET)* *electroencephalography (EEG)* and *Magnetoencephalography (MEG)*. Besides recordings of brain structure and function, health, clinical or genetic data can be collected, but also data in relation to cognitive and/or behavioral tasks, and demographic data that relates to health and/or development.

The legal requirements for sharing medical data are so overwhelming that often by the time they are cleared, the researchers (often PhD students) have already consumed an important part of their allocated time.

SIESTA would be a confidential third party platform for this use case, so that legal paperwork can be handled only once for the whole platform for each data providing entity. Subsequently, the DRHs at the data providing entity can use it to easily share their data with researchers without any further legal procedures.

The researchers' pipelines can be interactively developed and tested on the SIESTA platform on a scrambled (non-sensitive) version of the data, executed on the real (sensitive) data and the resulting group-level output data is anonymous, and as such can be shared in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Example user story:

UC2.E01.US01
 As a researcher, I want to be able to use restricted-access medical data without having to sign paperwork that delay my projects, so that I can quickly implement analyses on sensitive data to generate new research outputs

Use case 2 questionnaire	Annexes I - UC2
Use case 2 Personas-EPICs-User Stories document	Annexes II - UC2
Use case 2 DMPs	2.1 Input , 2.1 Output , 2.2 Input , 2.2 Output , 2.3 Input , 2.3 Output , 2.4 Input , 2.4 Output

Table 2. Important links and documents concerning use case 2.

3.4. USE CASE 3: ENERGY DOMAIN

The third use case, managed by WP16, is about confidential data usage in the energy domain. There's a lot of public backlash about real-time energy consumption data in personal habitats as it is related to private life habits and may also be related to people's security (home presence or absence is interesting, among others, for criminal activity). Such data is sensitive and its use warrants some precautions.

Yet renewable energy consumption data is of great importance to allow efficient energy management and distribution. Statistical analysis may enable policy makers to take informed decisions for the development of distribution networks or to help choose production site locations.

SIESTA aims to enable trusted and privacy-compliant energy domain data use for research and other purposes, in order to serve such goals and empower the society with better energy management. The data and processing will follow the FAIR principles so as to be easily peer-reviewed and reproducible.

The success of the platform may even allow seamless and even cross-border data sets access to enable more precise or accurate models to be created, allow reuse and valorization of technical information associated with energy consumption, production and storage.

Following the failure of the initial partner, a new partner from the same technological field will be selected to replace it. At the time of writing, the identity of the new partner is not known. In order not to delay the project, this version of the deliverable does not contain any additional information for this use case. It will be followed by a new version, D6.2, which will incorporate the data from the new partner.

3.5. USE CASE 4: TEXT ANONYMIZATION ON SENSITIVE DATA

The main objective of this use case, managed by WP17, is to develop a solution for anonymization or pseudonymization of unstructured texts containing sensitive data (information related to locations, organizations, addresses, emails, finance or any other information that could lead to identifying a person or organization), so that they can be disclosed for research purposes.

The research goal is to train a text classification model to ease the preliminary treatment of these documents (e.g., a Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) might need to make a first classification of written reports with cyber incidents depending on the type of incident prior to their analysis). This model should be usable for different languages and domains (e.g., cyber incident reports, Child Sexual Exploitation Material (CSEM), etc.)

For example: CERT team members would get incident reports uploaded into the platform, then create anonymized versions to share with researchers. The researchers can then train their AI classification models on the anonymized data to enhance them. They will then let CERT team members use the models on real incident reports.

The initially chosen domain for this use case, CSEM has legal requirements that hinder its adequateness for the initial SIESTA stages, and the use case chose to change to cyber incident investigation, which exhibits similar research characteristics, but for which data will be easier to get. This is not a problem for the SIESTA project, as the domain remains textual anonymization.

Example user story:

UC4.E01.US01
 As a CERT team member, I want to upload incident reports to the platform and create anonymized versions that can be shared to train classification models.

Use case 4 questionnaire	Annexes I - UC4
Use case 4 Personas-EPICs-User Stories document	Annexes II - UC4
Use case 4 DMP	DMP

Table 4. Important links and documents concerning use case 4.

3.6. USE CASE 5: DEMOGRAPHY

This use case, managed by WP18, is about the increasing needs for access to demographic data, being it for science purposes or policy decision-making, statistical analysis, etc. That kind of data is by definition of sensitive nature, to various levels, and its access needs to be carefully allowed to avoid situations where the individuals can be identified from cross-checking the different data sets.

To allow more data dissemination in accordance with the FAIR principles, the creation of compound anonymised data sets is essential, as the raw data cannot be shared easily.

This use case will produce tools to improve the anonymization of the data, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access.

The SIESTA platform will enable users to fulfill those needs by acting as a trustable third party, in which the confidential data sets can be processed in a way to allow results to be freely shared.

Example user story:

UC5.E03.US01
 As a data provider, I want to use advanced anonymization techniques within the platform, so that I can provide safe and usable data to researchers and policymakers.

Use case 5 questionnaire	Annexes I - UC5
Use case 5 Personas-EPICs-User Stories document	Annexes II - UC5
Use case 5 DMP	DMP

Table 5. Important links and documents concerning use case 5.

3.7. USE CASES SUMMARY

The different use cases share some common needs that the SIESTA platform will help fulfill. The different subjects that will need to be supported are:

- There should be a way to authenticate the different platform users (DRHs, scientists, results users, etc.) so that they each will only be allowed access to specific platform assets.
- There should be a way for DRHs to upload and enable access to their sensitive data from within the platform, but only to trusted & identified people. DRHs will need a way to assess that only those who were allowed have actually accessed the data.
- There should be a way to perform computing, analysis or processing of the data securely. This should be granted to researchers, students or other data users.
- There should be a way to get the processed results out of the platform to designated and allowed people.
- There should be a way to get auditing data for users to check and validate data uses.

These high level and abstract requirements will be investigated, then refined into technical choices in the next sections.

4. SIESTA INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDERS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The SIESTA infrastructure providers are pre-existing known actors from the science computing scene. They are already involved in a wide range of scientific, research-related computing, and the services they provide are massively used for all kinds of research subjects.

These efforts are ongoing for many years, and results in a vast pool of knowledge and expertise that the provider's personnel share with each other. Either directly through international cooperation in shared projects (e.g. EGI Federation, WLCG, EOSC, etc.), or less formally with participation in domain-specific technical working groups.

These infrastructure providers are handling vast amounts of data for diverse science domains like physics, chemistry, biology or social sciences, etc.

They are following the required security best practices established within the computer science domain to ensure a healthy platform with minimal disturbances from malware or other malicious activities.

4.2. CSIC / IFCA

The Spanish National Research Council –in Spanish *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (CSIC) – is the largest public institution dedicated to research in Spain. IFCA is one of the 139 specialized centers that composes CSIC, and it provides powerful computing capabilities and techniques since 2007 in response to the growing scientific project needs. IFCA has participated actively in diverse projects as a provider of Cloud Services, first contributor of the EGI Federated Cloud. Apart from that, IFCA belongs to the Spanish Supercomputing Network as a HPC node and contributes to the CMS experiment with Grid computing resources.

Available services:

- Cloud:
 - OpenStack IaaS with 118 heterogeneous nodes which provides 14.528 cores (Intel Xeon Platinum 8358 and AMD EPYC 7543)
 - 40 NVIDIA Tesla V100 and 80 NVIDIA Tesla T4.
- Block and Object Storage:
 - Ceph: 2.4 PB in total, with redundancy 1:3, almost 1 PB online.
 - GPFS for HPC but available for exporting to cloud in specific use cases: 3.5 PB with RAID 6.

Other characteristics relevant to the SIESTA project:

- 40 nodes with AMD EPYC 7543 cpu model available for Secure Encrypted Virtualization (AMD SEV).
- Coordination and participation in other innovative projects that deliver technological platforms for exploiting accelerated computing for the European Open Science Cloud such as AI4EOSC and iMagine.

Standardization:

- IFCA computing service is certified by the ISO / IEC 27001 and ISO / IEC 9001 since 2021 which ensures the quality and the implementation of security and privacy policies.
- In the beginning of 2024, IFCA was certified by the ENS-2024/0001, Spain's National Security Framework (ENS) which, integrated with the ISO 27001, establishes a robust security layer.

4.3. IISAS

The Institute of Informatics Slovak Academy of Sciences (IISAS) is an academic cloud provider integrated in the EGI Federated Cloud infrastructure and provides IaaS-type virtualized resources for EU and local scientific research projects. IISAS participated in many EU projects related to European research infrastructures since 2001 (CrossGrid, INT.EU.GRID, EGEE, EGEE-II, EGEE-III, EGI-InSPIRE, EGI-Engage, EOSC-hub, EGI-ACE) as a provider of HPC and Cloud services and operates National Grid Infrastructure for Slovakia (NGL_SK).

Available services:

- Cloud - OpenStack cloud compute infrastructure (53 nodes, 756 CPU cores, 11 NVIDIA A100 GPUs)
- Storage - OpenStack block storage (6TB Ceph, 350TB NFS)

Other characteristics relevant to the SIESTA project:

- Two nodes with AMD EPYC 7443P CPUs supporting AMD Infinity Guard (TSME, SEV, SEV-ES, SEV-SMP) will be added to IISAS Cloud infrastructure and provided for the SIESTA testbed infrastructure.
- OpenStack version Ussuri (AMD-SEV support will be added on compatible nodes).

Other relevant services provided by IISAS:

- Secrets Store service: Highly-available, distributed deployment of Hashicorp Vault for secret management
- Dynamic DNS service: for registering hostnames and their dynamic assignments to servers on Clouds

4.4. CNRS / IPHC

The French National Centre for Scientific Research – in french Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (*CNRS*) –, as the largest research organization for fundamental science in Europe that covers all scientific fields, has a dedicated computing service and e-infrastructure system.

CNRS operates two major national computing centers, IDRIS (INS2I) in Orsay dedicated to High Performance Computing (HPC) computing and CC-IN2P3 (IN2P3) in Lyon, specialized in High Throughput Computing (HTC) and data management.

These two national-level computing centers are completed with regional infrastructures providing custom digital services for research.

IPHC is an institute whose supervisory bodies are the CNRS and the University of Strasbourg, and which hosts one of these regional centers, structured as a platform called SCIGNE. This platform has been involved in several H2020 projects, like EOSC-Pillar, EGI-ACE or GreenDigit. Its IaaS cloud computing service has been integrated within the EGI Federation since 2015.

Available services:

- Cloud - OpenStack IaaS Cloud with 20 heterogeneous nodes (1640 CPU cores, 11 TB of RAM, 13 GPUs)
- Storage - CEPH-based block storage (1.5 PB)

Other characteristics relevant to the SIESTA project:

- Two nodes with AMD EPYC 9534 CPUs supporting AMD Infinity Guard (TSME, SEV, SEV-ES, SEV-SMP) will be added to the SCIGNE Cloud infrastructure and provided for the SIESTA infrastructure during WP7.
- OpenStack Magnum service is available, which provides containers as a service.
- A container image registry is available. Based on the Harbor software, it offers a secure way to manage Docker and APTainer images, including security scan and signature features.

Standardization:

- The platform is working towards ISO / IEC 9001 certification.

5. STATE OF THE ART – AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY SCOUTING

5.1. INTRODUCTION TO CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

As already explained in the Introduction, confidential Computing is about End-to-end encryption:

- Encryption at rest: Data encryption at storage (See Storage section below)
- Encryption in transit: Network security (See Networking section below)
- Encryption in use: Confidential computing (See Computing section below)

We will now introduce some concepts and technologies related or required to implement secure confidential computing, some will be presented with more details in the later chapters.

5.1.1. Trusted Execution Environments and related concepts

Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) is an *isolated and secure environment*, also called an *enclave*, for data processing. The data is protected by encryption on input and output, but most importantly *the data is protected from interception or unwanted modification even from entities residing in the system where the data processing happens, including privileged processes (kernel, hypervisor)*.

TEEs differ by complexity. There are TEEs without a secure register area, for example smart cards, which support stateless functions, and there are more complex TEEs with secure registers, which can remember state between calls, and thus can support stateful functions and whole processing systems. The latter are the main objective of current research, as is their implementation in general computational environments which would support standard user applications. The goal of the research is to provide TEEs which would feature:

- integrity and privacy of data
- general purpose computation
- high performance of computation

TEEs rely on a broad range of security mechanisms. Apart from incoming/outgoing data channel encryption, a TEE must ensure integrity of its own execution. This is achieved by the combination of:

- [secure boot](#) - when the host starts, secure boot loads immutable and verified images into an enclave to ensure a chain of trust among the enclave images, operating system components, and configurations. Before the operating system starts, a secure boot ensures the TEE is loaded correctly and no hosts, even the hypervisor, can tamper with it.
- [isolated execution](#) - TEE loads user-defined programs into enclaves and then performs isolated execution for each program. During execution, sensitive data (including code and data) is maintained in EPCs (Enclave Page Caches) within the PRM (Processor Reserved Memory), which is pre-configured in DRAM in the

bootstrapping phase. The code loaded inside an enclave can access both non-PRM and PRM memory. On the other hand, external programs cannot access any data in the PRM memory.

- [sealing](#) - analogous to EPC and PRM, sealing is a mechanism to let a TEE securely persist and retrieve “secrets” on the local disk. Sealing binds the secrets to a specific enclave identity by a sealing key derived from the CPU hardware. Using the sealing key, TEE encrypts the enclave’s secrets and stores them on a local disk. Conversely, TEE retrieves the secrets from the disk by unsealing (decrypting) them.
- [attestation](#) - establishes trust between an enclave and another enclave or a remote machine by building a secure channel. There are two attestation mechanisms: local attestation and remote attestation. While two enclaves on the same platform can attest to each other using local attestation, remote attestation allows a client to verify that its program is configured and executed correctly (i.e., not modified or tampered with) in a remote server.

The most important hardware component which supports TEEs, especially the secure boot (which cannot be achieved without dedicated hardware support) is the [Trusted Platform Module](#). It is a physical device residing in the computer (on the motherboard or even directly in the CPU), which uses cryptography to help securely store essential and critical information on the computer to enable platform authentication. The stored information is used - among others - to verify the booting process and detect any modifications to the BIOS and operating system, which would invalidate the TEE's security guarantees.

5.1.2. Authentication & Users management

Manages identities mapping from real world people (that may have signed legal documents) to identities within the platform that are securely granted access permissions to specific platform assets & resources. The most common services and technologies implementing such features in the EOSC realm are:

The [OpenID](#) authentication technology can be used to implement authentication for the SIESTA project.

The following software may be of interest:

- [Keycloak](#)
- [Indigo-IAM](#)

The platform may allow projects to bring their own identity provider and/or provide one for projects that don't have nor want to manage one themselves.

Platform identities may also be associated within groups to make their management more straightforward.

5.1.3. Access Control

The management of access control will be closely aligned with GitOps principles, ensuring that security and operational policies are not just static configurations but dynamic components that evolve alongside the infrastructure. GitOps, which emphasizes declarative configurations stored in version control and automated deployment processes, provides a robust framework for enforcing consistent and auditable access controls across all environments. By integrating access control management into GitOps workflows, organizations can ensure that authorization policies are applied in real-time, automatically adjusting to changes in the environment as they occur. This dynamic approach reduces the risk of human error, enhances security posture, and ensures that access policies remain aligned with the overall state of the infrastructure.

For a more comprehensive coverage of the broader operations strategy, refer to Chapter 5.1.12 on DevSecOps. There, the topic expands on how DevSecOps principles further apply in a broader context and what tools are expected to be used for example for ensuring the correct policies are applied for a given scenario. In essence, the application of authorization policies in this context becomes a fluid, automated process that adapts as needed, ensuring that security is maintained without hindering the agility and responsiveness of the operational environments.

5.1.4. Data Ingestion

Sensitive data may need some level of anonymization or pseudonymization either before entering the platform or as a preliminary stage before being made available to the computing pipelines.

First, it is important to remove all the information that can be linked with an identifiable or identified individual. In this sense, such attributes can be suppressed when anonymizing the data, or they can be pseudonymized (e.g. applying hash functions, randomized values, etc).

In addition, when dealing with tabular data it must be taken into account that in some cases the combination of certain information/attributes (quasi-identifiers) may allow one to identify an individual within the dataset. In this line, different anonymity techniques can be applied once the data is ingested for preventing information extraction and different attacks.

On the other hand, in the case of other kinds of data, such as images or videos, obscuration techniques can be applied to prevent information extraction from a certain sensitive part of the image/video, in order to prevent the extraction of personally identifiable information from such data.

5.1.5. Audit Systems

The platform will need a tamper-proof audit system so that users can entrust their data and computing without fear of unauthorized access. They should be able to see who has accessed the data they entrusted into the platform, who performed which computations, etc. This entails both access monitoring and logging, as well as a way to query the resulting data for specific patterns.

Although the usage of blockchain or other distributed ledger technologies may seem suitable for such a task, there is no need to have a distributed system and there are no trust or control issues over the data store of the audit system. In this case, the concepts presented in the Verifiable Data Structures from Eijdenberg, Laurie and Cutler 2015⁸ to provide transparency to services in order to verify trust seems much more suitable.

Currently, the following two different software products are being considered:

- [BBVA QED](#): is an open-source software that allows users to establish trust relationships by leveraging verifiable cryptographic proofs. QED implements a forward-secure append-only persistent authenticated data structure. Each append operation produces as a result a cryptographic structure (a signed snapshot), which acts as a receipt for the operation
- [Google Trillian](#): Open source product that implements a highly scalable and cryptographically verifiable data store as a gRPC service. The Trillian ecosystem includes other products such as [Distributor](#) and [Witness](#), providing services to ensure that logs are evolving in an append-only manner and counter-signs checkpoints from any previously witnessed checkpoints.

One of the main differences between the two is the data store. Whereas Trillian is opinionated in its implementation (i.e. imposing a MySQL database) QED does not impose any data layer, and it is up to the user to select which one to use.

5.1.6. Storage

Secure Storage must provide access to storage space in a safe way for both the computing environment (operating system volumes) and data needed by the use cases. This entails both secrecy and tampering resistance.

There are many possibilities for secure data storage, both with proprietary and open solutions.

For sensitive data at rest, encrypted volumes aka full disk encryption (FDE) technologies are available. In order to avoid having the encryption keys available to platform operators, everything has to happen *inside* the confidential compute element: key management and volume on-the-fly decryption.

Also, we need to ensure operating system volumes remain trustable. That means what has been validated has not been maliciously modified.

To ensure forward secrecy of the chosen encryption scheme, we may choose to securely wipe the volumes before returning them to the lower layers (hypervisor or container orchestrator). Even if this is not strictly needed assuming today's cryptographic techniques are not broken, we should not assume they never will be. The techniques to be used differ between the different hardware technologies used by the physical layer: mechanical hard disk drives (because of magnetic remanence) and flash-based storage (because of sector reallocation and overprovisioning). There are defined standards to ensure regulatory compliance (HIPAA [4], ISO 27001 [17], etc.).

- dm-crypt

⁸ <https://github.com/google/trillian/blob/master/docs/papers/VerifiableDataStructures.pdf>

- dm-integrity
- dm-verity

Full disk encryption through the use of dm-crypt, is both open and secure, but care must be applied to ensure up-to-date masterkey protection (LUKS2 format with argon2 PBKDF, when applicable).

5.1.7. Networking

Secure networking is a really mature field which already enables end-to-end encrypted communications, as proven and standardized protocols, including most notably:

- Transport Layer Security ([TLS](#))
- Virtual Private Networking ([VPN](#))
- Secure Shell ([SSH](#))

But cryptographic key management is still required and should be handled with care to avoid undermining the communication channel's security.

5.1.8. Computing

The means to easily provision computing resources to end users in cloud environments can be via operating system virtualization (Virtual Machines, VM) or application virtualization (containers, CoCo). Both methods have different characteristics and provide different sets of features or limitations. Regardless of the chosen technology, both the host and guest systems need to be secured properly to ensure the whole platform remains trustworthy.

For confidential computing, two components need to be cooperative: memory and CPU. To ensure no rogue device with direct memory access (DMA) can steal data, IOMMUs and memory encryption technologies are used. To ensure confidentiality of the virtual machine (guest) against the hypervisor (host), the CPU has to provide some ways to protect its state and data (cache content, register values, etc.) during context transitions.

CPU vendors provide different technologies tailored to CC, they are not all at the same level of readiness, or usefulness for proper CC. And only some CPU models provide the right set of features.

- AMD : SME, SEV, SEV-ES, SEV-SNP, SEV-TIO
- Intel : SGX, TDX
- ARM : CCA
- AWS : Nitro enclaves
- Apple : [Secure Enclave Processor \(SEP\)](#)

Some of these technologies are not currently interesting, for example, the Amazon one is proprietary, and does not provide CC virtual machines (VM). ARM CCA is not at the same maturity level as Intel or AMD technologies. This will certainly change in the future and may need reconsideration, when they get more mainstream.

Intel or AMD, even if more mature, still require very recent hardware (generation 3 or 4 for EPYC, generation 4 or 5 for Xeon) and linux kernel support, which is only available in recent distributions.

5.1.9. Hardware Accelerators

The computing pipelines that will run on the SIESTA platform will sometimes need access to specific hardware accelerators, such as GPU, NPU, etc. This should not put the rest of the computing confidentiality or security at risk. Not all hardware will be suitable, nor all means to provide access to it. Current technology may not allow for PCI device passthrough, for example, or require the copy of all data through bounce buffers, so negatively impacting performance. This area is subject to change a lot with emerging technologies such as PCI devices authentication, SEV-TIO, or Nvidia Hopper architecture which boasts some new confidential accelerators features (virtual GPU). However, it is worth noticing that some of these functionalities may require the use of proprietary technologies.

Proper secure support for hardware accelerators may be provided in further iterations on the SIESTA platform.

In addition to the caveats above, the scarcity of the accelerators (compared to CPU, RAM & storage) and the inability to partition and share them can impose the use of some kind of reservation mechanism to ensure fair access to the shared resources. For example, the [OpenStack Blazar](#) Resource Reservation Service can be used to manage access reservations.

5.1.10. Entropy

The software encryption required at different levels of the CC stack for storage or network will need trustworthy random numbers in sufficient volume. This entropy source is called a random number generator ([RNG](#)). This should not be trivially dismissed as it is the foundation of nearly all secure cryptographic key generation algorithms.

The randomness quality provided to the guest systems should stay trustable at all times. In particular, it should not be manipulated by an external environment (hypervisor (HV) or another VM on the same HV).

The depletion of the random number source entails a greater security risk. The fact that multiple VMs or containers will run, and as such consume the available entropy, on the same hardware platform will make this problem worse.

The current way is to provide entropy from the host system to the guest through a virtual random number generator (virtio-rng), this may not be suitable as we should not rely on the host / hypervisor for security. Without this, VMs have not a lot of reliable entropy sources and randomness quality and availability will suffer.

In any case, the compute platform should not rely on a single source of entropy and mix different ones in a cryptographically sensible way, so that even if one source is compromised, it will not lose quality but only random number performance.

The platform may provide access to dedicated hardware-based random number generators (HWRNG), a Trusted Platform Module ([TPM](#)) provided RNG or allow the use of dedicated CPU instructions ([RDRAND](#)) which may help alleviate these concerns.

5.1.11. Time management

Accurate timekeeping is also important, as secure network protocols or certificates are heavily relying on this. The platform must ensure that proper distribution and synchronization of accurate time sources are in place and effective. A pool of trustable timekeeping sources should be provided in a tamper-proof way. The platform users should not trust the SIESTA platform for its time sources, but use a secure way to obtain high quality time data.

The [Network Time Security \(RFC 8915\)](#) protocol (NTS) has been established to harden NTPv4 security with the addition of authenticated encryption and [TLS](#). For example, the use of the [chrony](#) server for timekeeping with a NTS-supported upstream server will enhance time management security within the platform.

5.1.12. DevSecOps

The topic of DevSecOps is one of the two foundational pillars of the WP12, which will be fully realized in the second half of this project timeline. While the full implementation of these strategies will occur in WP12, selected elements will also be introduced earlier WP7. This selective implementation will serve as a pilot, allowing the team to test and refine key aspects of the DevSecOps approach before scaling them up in the latter stages of the project.

Recent developments in the [DevSecOps](#) domain reflect a significant emphasis on automation, AI, and machine learning to enhance security and streamline processes. Organizations have been increasingly integrating security earlier in the software development lifecycle, a practice known as "shift-left" security, to proactively address vulnerabilities and reduce remediation costs.

Another key trend is the consolidation of security tools, which simplifies the security architecture and enhances visibility across the development pipeline. This consolidation allows for a more unified and comprehensive security strategy. The maturation of cloud-native security practices is also notable, with a focus on securing containerized and serverless environments, addressing the unique challenges posed by these technologies

The topic of DevSecOps, in general, covers services Code repository and Software mirror of Secure Compute in Conceptual Architecture. The DevSecOps tooling will include vulnerability scanning and tracking ([SBOM](#)), misconfiguration prevention, artifacts verification and signing, and access and secret management.

List of technologies:

- Compliance testing / policy enforcement
 - [Gatekeeper](#)
 - [Confest](#)
 - [Open Policy Agent](#)
- Secure supply chain
 - [Nexus](#)
- Artefact signing & verifying
 - [Cosign](#)
- Security scanner
 - [Trivy](#)

- Secure artifacts repository
 - [Harbor](#)
- Code quality
 - [SonarQube](#)

Development management

With everything-as-code becoming the norm in the [DevOps](#) landscape, the platform will need to use a tool to handle all the development related activities. Such as code evolution tracking, issues management, code reviews, documentation, etc.

A wide range of tools exists in this field:

- [GitLab](#)
- [Github](#)
- [Codeberg](#)
- [Perforce](#)

Some of those solutions can be self-hosted, the other ones being services provided by private companies or non-profit organizations.

Monitoring & Alerting

In order to ensure the continuous health, availability of the platform and that the performance stays within the acceptable range, monitoring its dynamic state will be mandatory. The resource providers will already have something to handle the lower levels of the stack, for the services they provide, but the platform as a whole will also need to provide aggregated data, centralized reporting and alerting in case something is not working properly.

- [Grafana](#) (metrics visualization, dashboards)
- [Prometheus](#) (metrics storage, visualization & alerting)
- [Graphite](#) (metrics storage & visualization)
- [ElasticSearch](#) (log storage, search & analytics) + Kibana (Dashboard)
- [InfluxDB](#) (metrics storage) + [Telegraf](#) (metrics collection)
- [Netdata](#) (metrics collection & more)
- [Collectd](#) (metrics collection)
- [Ceilometer](#) (OpenStack metrics collection)

Secrets management

The platform will need to manage, store and distribute sensitive data (passwords, encryption keys, certificates, miscellaneous secrets, etc.). This will be a very important part of the platform's security, as a lot of other things will depend on it.

- [Barbican](#)
- [OpenBao](#) (the fork of [Hashicorp Vault](#))
- [Bitwarden Secrets Manager](#)
- [AWS Secrets Manager](#)

For example, the use of the OpenStack Barbican service with an Hardware Security Module (HSM) backend storage is deemed sufficiently secure by [EDF Exaion](#) Cloud security team.

HSM hardware is available from the following suppliers:

- [YubiHSM](#) by Yubico (USB, ~1K€)
- [NetHSM](#) from NitroKey (Network, ~10K€)
- [Luna HSM](#) from Thalès (Network, ~100K€)

Some of those projects can also provide a source of random bytes, see the above “Entropy” chapter).

Workload sandboxing

In the context of the project SIESTA, ensuring the security of containerized analytical workloads is more critical than ever. The enhanced security of workload sandboxing is looking to leverage the eBPF (extended Berkeley Packet Filter) technology to provide fine-grained, kernel-level security policies and high-performance packet processing. This ensures robust protection and minimal latency for containerized applications.

Partially covering service of the Compute environment of Secure Compute in conceptual architecture. Securing the sensitive data against potentially malicious, and at the design time unknown, workloads trying to access the data they are not explicitly allowed to.

Cilium is an open-source project that provides high-performance networking, security, and observability for containerized environments, especially those using Kubernetes. Cilium is tightly integrated with eBPF, a powerful and efficient technology in the Linux kernel that allows for the execution of sandboxed programs within the kernel.

List of technologies:

- High-performance secure network interface for containers (Kubernetes)
 - [Cilium CNI](#)
- Cilium Network Policies for L3/L4 level communication
 - [CiliumNetworkPolicy](#)
- Service Mesh for L7 level communication
 - [Cilium Service Mesh](#)
 - [Istio](#)

5.2. CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING SOFTWARE PROJECTS

A summary table for the following CC projects is located in [Annexes IV](#).

5.2.1. Gramine

Applications programmed for one system often do not work on another. Gramine bridges this gap by hoisting application-facing code from the operating system (OS) kernel into a userspace library. Gramine uses a platform adaptation layer (PAL) that is easy to implement on a new host system. As long as a system implements the PAL interface, all of POSIX/Linux will follow.

Gramine is a library OS, similar to a unikernel. Compared to running a complete guest OS in a virtual machine (VM), Gramine is much lighter weight. Work is ongoing to integrate Gramine with Docker containers.

A particular use case for Gramine is Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX), where applications do not work out-of-the-box. Gramine solves this problem, with the added security benefits. Gramine can serve as a compatibility layer on other platforms.

Gramine runs unmodified applications inside Intel SGX. It supports dynamically loaded libraries, runtime linking, multi-process abstractions, and file authentication. For additional security, Gramine performs cryptographic and semantic checks at an untrusted host interface. Developers provide a manifest file to configure the application environment and isolation policies, Gramine automatically does the rest.

Evaluation:

- **Maturity:** production (version 1.7 from April 24, 2024)
- **Development activity:** active (22 commits/month to main, April 15, 2024 – May 15, 2024)
- **Installation requirements:** Intel SGX platform
- License: LGPL 3.0
- **Complexity of installation:** easy (package repositories for Debian 22/11, Ubuntu 22.04/20.04, AlmaLinux 9/8)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** No, only to re-build app with SGX
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** The Gramine Shielded Containers (GSC) tool transforms a base Docker image into a new, “graminized” image.
- **App executions (how to run an app):** run with ‘gramine-sgx app’

Links:

- <https://gramineproject.io/>
- <https://github.com/gramineproject>

5.2.2. Islet

Islet is an open-source software project written in Rust that enables confidential computing on ARM architecture devices using the ARMv9 CCA. The primary objective of Islet is to enable on-device confidential computing and protect user privacy on end user devices.

While current confidential computing solutions mainly focus on server-side protection, it is equally important to safeguard user information at the user device level, since that is where private data collection initially occurs. Furthermore, as more and more users rely on privacy apps such as private messengers, secure emails, password managers, and web browsers with privacy settings, there is a growing need to ensure privacy on user devices. Islet, an open-source project, addresses this need by providing a platform for ARM-based confidential computing.

Feature Overview

- Realm Management Monitor
- Hardware Enforced Security
- Confidential Computing API Standardization
- Automated Verification

Evaluation:

- **Maturity:** production (version 1.0)
- **Development activity:** active (43 commits/month to main, April 15, 2024 – May 15, 2024)
- **Installation requirements:** ARMv9 CCA
- **License:** Apache 2.0 (copyright: Samsung Electronics Co.)
- **Complexity of installation:** medium (only source code in the release)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** optionally, SDK provided
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** binary
- **App executions (how to run an app):** using Islet RMM (Realm Management Monitor)

Links:

- <https://github.com/islet-project/islet>
- https://islet-project.github.io/islet/components/cca_design.html#islet-implementation

5.2.3. Keystone RISC-V enclave

Keystone RISC-V enclave (which is not related to OpenStack Keystone service) is an open-source project that builds trusted execution environments (TEEs) for RISC-V systems. Its hardware-enforced and software-defined memory isolation enables trusted computing (a.k.a. confidential computing) with various threat models and

functionalities. The implementation is platform-agnostic, making Keystone portable across different RISC-V platforms with minimal engineering efforts.

Keystone has seen a large amount of adoption in academia, however, lacks a driving force from the industry, which is required for Keystone to be successful. The main reasons:

- **Hardware Availability:** Many people entering Keystone suffer from a lack of server-class RISC-V chips in the market. Moreover, even existing chips don't usually have the root of trust that Keystone requires.
- **Missing Killer App:** There is no "killer app", which makes more sense to run in Keystone than in other existing platforms (e.g., SGX) that have better hardware availability.
- **Usability:** It is not trivial to understand how Keystone works, and to make a particular program run in an enclave. Also, it is really hard to debug programs running in Keystone.
- **General Limitations:** There are general limitations that Keystone suffers from its design. For example, the number of enclaves is limited by the number of PMP entries, and the enclaves cannot shrink or expand their physical memory without fragmentation.

Evaluation:

- **Maturity:** production (ver. 1.0.0)
- **Development activity:** not very active (1 commits/month to main, April 15, 2024 – May 15, 2024), latest release March 2, 2021
- **Installation requirements:** RISC-V platform with Physical memory protection (PMP), was tested on CVA6 (Tape-out, Simulation, FPGA Emulation) and SiFive HiFive Unleashed (Development Board)
- **License:** BSD-3-Clause
- **Complexity of installation:** medium (need to build from source)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** yes, a full system for using a Keystone enclave consists of possibly writing 3 things: Host (userspace, outside enclave, untrusted) - Runtime (system level, inside enclave, trusted) - Enclave app (userspace, inside enclave, trusted)
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** binary
- **App executions (how to run an app):** Keystone can be run using QEMU, FireSim (FPGA), or the SiFive HiFive Unleashed board.

Links:

- <https://keystone-enclave.org/>
- <https://github.com/keystone-enclave>

5.2.4. Certifier Framework For Confidential Computing

The Certifier API greatly simplifies and unifies programming and operations support for multi-vendor Confidential Computing platforms by providing simple client trust

management, including attestation evaluation, secure storage, platform initialization, secret sharing, secure channels and other services. It consists of a client API called the Certifier API and server-based policy evaluation server called the Certifier Service.

- **Maturity:** beta (version 0.1.1 from Aug 30, 2022)
- **Development activity:** active (3 commits in May 2024, over 1,000 commits in last 20 months)
- **Installation requirements:** Intel SGX platform; can also run on a simulated enclave for development and testing
- **License:** Apache 2.0
- **Complexity of installation:** medium (requires installation of standard Ubuntu packages but not additional software; requires C++ build and following a detailed list of steps)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** Yes, app needs to include artifacts necessary for certification
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** binary, with additional artifacts in files
- **App executions (how to run an app):** standard run as a binary, with additional certification-related parameters

Links:

- <https://github.com/ccf-certifier-framework/certifier-framework-for-confidential-computing>
- <https://github.com/ccf-certifier-framework/certifier-framework-for-confidential-computing/blob/main/INSTALL.md>

5.2.5. COCONUT-SVSM

The COCONUT-SVSM is an implementation of a Secure VM Service Module for confidential computing virtual machines (CVMs). It runs within the TCB of the CVM and aims to support three operational modes:

1. Service Module Mode
2. Paravisor Mode
3. Service VM Mode

With its ability to provide secure services, the COCONUT-SVSM aims to become a platform to execute host hypervisor services within the trusted context of the CVM and reduce the interface between the hypervisor and the CVM OS. It acts as a proxy between the hypervisor and the CVM OS to reduce the need to harden the CVM OS from malicious hypervisor input.

- **Maturity:** in development, no stable version released
- **Development activity:** active (dense commit activity in the last 3 months, over 1,500 commits since Mar 2023)

- **Installation requirements:** AMD EPYC Generation 3 or newer processor, SEV-SNP enabled in the BIOS settings, Linux host and guest kernels, EDK2 with SVSM support
- **License:** MIT
- **Complexity of installation:** complex - building multiple complex components (QEMU, firmware, image) with SVSM and IGVM support, then building the software itself
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** not applicable; as for guest OS, can be both without and with SVSM support
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** not applicable
- **App executions (how to run an app):** not applicable

Links:

- <https://github.com/confidential-computing/governance/tree/main/Projects#coconut-svsm>
- https://static.sched.com/hosted_files/kvmforum2022/ca/SEV-SNP-Confidential-Guest-Services-with-SVSM.pdf

5.2.6. Enarx

Enarx is a framework for running applications in TEE instances – which we refer to as “Keeps” – without the need to trust lots of dependencies, without the need to rewrite the application, and without the need to implement attestation separately. Enarx aims to minimize the trust relationships required when executing applications, meaning that the only components which need to be trusted are: the CPU and associated firmware, the workload itself, and the Enarx middleware, which is fully open source and auditable. Applications run without any of the layers in the stack (e.g. hypervisor, kernel, user-space) being able to look into or alter the Keep or its contents.

- **Maturity:** mature, stable versions for Windows, macOS, Linux
- **Development activity:** medium (approx 1 commit a month in the last 6 months, with 2,500 commits since Sep 2019)
- **Installation requirements:** Intel SGX or AMD SEV-SNP TEEs; has the ability to run without these for development purposes
- **License:** Apache 2.0
- **Complexity of installation:** easy - packages provided; installation from source possible, detailed instructions are provided
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** yes, needs to be compiled in WebAssembly
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** via publishing into a repository
- **App executions (how to run an app):** deployment of a published app from repository

Links:

- <https://enarx.dev/>

5.2.7. Occlum

Occlum is a system that enables secure and efficient multitasking in a LibOS for Intel SGX. Different from prior work on SGX LibOSes, it explores an opportunity of synergy between compiler techniques and LibOS design. Specifically, implements the LibOS processes as SFI-Isolated Processes (SIPs), which reside alongside the LibOS in the single address space of an enclave. Occlum makes running applications inside enclaves easy. It allows one to run unmodified programs inside enclaves with just a few simple commands. And Occlum is open-source and free to use.

- **Maturity:** beta version (0.30.1) for Linux
- **Development activity:** high (approx 7 commits a month in the last 6 months, with 1411 commits since Feb 2019)
- **Installation requirements:** Intel SGX or Intel FLC; limited ability to run without these for development purposes
- **License:** BSD
- **Complexity of installation:** easy - pre-built Occlum docker container, detailed instructions are provided
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** yes, needs to be compiled by occlum-gcc
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** using occlum commands: init, build and run
- **App executions (how to run an app):** using occlum commands: init, build and run

Links:

- <https://occlum.io/>
- <https://github.com/occlum/occlum>
- <https://occlum.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

5.2.8. Open Enclave SDK

The Open Enclave SDK is a hardware-agnostic open source library for developing applications that utilize Hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments, also known as Enclaves. Open Enclave (OE) is an SDK for building enclave applications in C and C++. Open Enclave SDK aims to generalize the development of enclave applications across TEEs from different hardware vendors. The current implementation provides support for Intel SGX as well as preview support for OP-TEE OS on ARM TrustZone. As an open source project, OpenEnclave SDK also strives to provide a transparent solution that is agnostic to specific vendors, service providers and choice of operating systems.

- **Maturity:** mature, stable versions for Windows and Linux
- **Development activity:** medium (approx 4 commits a month in the last 6 months, with 8345 commits since Aug 2017)
- **Installation requirements:** Intel SGX or AMD SEV-SNP TEEs; has the ability to run without these for development purposes
- **License:** MIT
- **Complexity of installation:** easy - packages provided; detailed instructions are provided

- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** no (compiled by CMake or GNU Make)
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** just to build by GNU make build
- **App executions (how to run an app):** just to run GNU make run

Links:

- <https://openenclave.io/sdk/>
- <https://github.com/openenclave/openenclave>

5.2.9. SPDM Tools

SPDM Tools project provides a Rust language implementation of [SPDM](#), [IDE_KM](#) and [TDISP](#). These protocols are used to facilitate direct device assignment for Trusted Execution Environment I/O (TEE-I/O) in Confidential Computing. There are a number of use cases that benefit from including devices and accelerators in the trust boundary of a Confidential Virtual Machine (CVM).

- **Maturity:** beta, just proof of concept for Linux and Windows (mingw)
- **Development activity:** medium (approx 10 commits a month in the last 6 months, with 79 commits since Nov 2023)
- **Installation requirements:** TEE, able to run in simulation mode
- **License:** Apache 2.0 or MIT
- **Complexity of installation:** medium - all compilers and tools must be installed, not so detailed instructions are provided
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** not relevant
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** not relevant
- **App executions (how to run an app):** not relevant

Links:

- <https://github.com/ccs-spdm-tools/spdm-rs>

5.2.10. Veracruz

Veracruz is a framework that can address privacy-preserving computations among mistrusting users from a given group. This framework uses strong isolation technology and remote attestation protocols to establish a more secure neutral ground within which a collaborative computation occurs on an untrusted environment (device). Additionally, privacy-preserving collaborative machine learning, secret auctions, elections or polls, and surveys are other special use cases that the framework supports.

The framework computations are special-purpose WebAssembly binaries, compiled against a small SDK which Veracruz provides. The binaries act as a sandbox, pinning down the behavior of the program, and allow it to abstract over the various strong isolation technologies that Veracruz supports.

However, since the Veracruz framework can be deployed from a docker container (Linux-based), the security requirements should start from there. No matter what

configurations are needed for the workspace, the docker group on the environment should be properly established, i.e. (who can add who, what can be read, who has write access, etc). Failure to do so may result in the entire Linux system being jeopardized, not only the abuse of the docker container but also the machine that hosts the container from the network. Subsequently, some post-exploitation techniques can be further addressed.

- **Maturity:** Stable version veracruz/base:v23.12 for Linux system
- **Development activity:** Still under improvement. However, the last release was on May 9th, 2024.
- **Installation requirements:** Docker installation
- **License:** MIT
- **Complexity of installation:** Easy (package repositories for Debian 22/11, Ubuntu 22.04/20.04, e.g: Kali 2021-2023)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** Needs to be compiled in WebAssembly, SDK also provided
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** Containers
- **App executions (how to run an app):** not relevant

Links:

- <https://veracruz-project.com/>
- <https://github.com/veracruz-project>

5.2.11. VERAISON

VERAISON is a concept derived from VERification of atteStatiON. Generally, an attestation is a system by which a user makes evidence about himself that another instance can utilize to determine the trustworthiness of that user. Implementing trust always requires confirmation; that is to say, based on that evidence, a verification phase is performed to confirm that it meets a policy established to prove trustworthiness. This activity is mostly done by comparing the evidence against cryptographic signatures for example, from a known trusted authority. Note that this can be a complicated scenario and is thus usually performed by a trusted verification service instead of a user (administrator of a system for example).

Verification Service solution that can address all deployments for a technology that needs to produce Attestation reports to prove its trustworthiness is not an easy task. It is more realistic that each deployment has its custom service since different requirements might be involved. Thus, the goal of VERAISON is to provide consistency and convenience in solving this issue by developing the software components that can be used to build Attestation Verification Services.

- **Maturity:** Mature, Linux system
- **Development activity:** Still under improvement. However, updates were released on May 15th, 2024.

- **Installation requirements:** Linux-based OS (Ubuntu 22, Kali 2021-2023 for example), Docker install
- **Licence:** Apache-2.0
- **Complexity of installation:** Easy (make sure to meet the installation requirements)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** Not applicable
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** Containers
- **App executions (how to run an app):** not relevant

Links:

- <https://github.com/veraison/services>
- <https://github.com/veraison/docs/blob/main/repo-guide.md>
- <https://github.com/orgs/veraison/repositories?type=all>

5.2.12. VirTEE

VirTee is a virtual tee Open Community. A tee is technically a system that provides a level of security of the following three (3) properties:

Data confidentiality: involves that, unallowed entities (users) cannot access, or view data while it is in use within the TEE.

Data integrity: involves that, unauthorized users cannot delete, add, or modify data that is in use within the TEE.

Code integrity: similar to the second one above with a slight difference, in that the unallowed user cannot alter any code executing in the TEE.

This Open Community is dedicated to building FLOSS components to facilitate the construction of Virtualization-based TEEs (Trusted Execution Environments) using Hardware-assisted Virtualization and other technologies such as Intel TDX, AMD SEV-SNP, and Armv9 Realms.

- **Maturity:** 1.2 Updated the code to match the library SEV-SNP update. Linux system.
- **Development activity:** active since July 2023
- **Installation requirements:** 3rd Gen or later AMD EPYC processors, You should always use the latest SEV firmware supported by your BIOS to have the latest features and security protection. The VirTEE/sev SEV-SNP features are compatible with firmware (version 1.54.01). SEV-SNP development is ongoing. AMD recommends using the latest host patches (<https://github.com/AMDESE/linux/tree/snp-host-latest>) for the Linux kernel until this support is upstream.
- **Licence:** Apache-2.0
- **Complexity of installation:** Easy (make sure to meet the installation requirements)
- **App adaptation (any modifications of app needed?):** Not applicable
- **App deployments (containers, binary):** Binaries
- **App executions (how to run an app):** not relevant

Links:

- <https://virtee.io/>
- <https://www.amd.com/content/dam/amd/en/documents/developer/58217-epyc-9004-ug-platform-attestation-using-virtee-snp.pdf>

5.3. SUPPORT FOR CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING IN CLOUD MIDDLEWARES

5.3.1. Support for Confidential Computing in OpenStack

OpenStack is a free, open standard cloud computing platform. It is mostly deployed as infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) in both public and private clouds.

AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV)

AMD's SEV (Secure Encrypted Virtualization) is a technology to protect virtual machines by transparently encrypting the memory of each VM with a unique key. SEV can also calculate a signature of the memory contents, which can be sent to the VM's owner as an attestation that the memory was encrypted correctly by the firmware.

[OpenStack supports AMD-SEV](#) since the "Train" release with following limitations:

Limitations which may be removed in the future as the hardware, firmware, and various software layers receive new features:

- SEV-encrypted VMs cannot yet be live-migrated or suspended, therefore they will need to be fully shut down before migrating off a SEV host, e.g. if maintenance is required on that host.
- SEV-encrypted VMs cannot contain directly accessible host devices (PCI passthrough). So for example, mdev vGPU support will not currently work. However technologies based on vhost-user should work fine.
- The boot disk type of SEV-encrypted VMs can only be virtio.
- SEV instances can only be booted from images which have the `hw_firmware_type` property set to `uefi`, and only when the machine type is set to `q35` (no IDE bus => no CD ROM for cloud-init config drive)

The following limitations are expected long-term:

- The number of SEV guests allowed to run concurrently will always be limited by the maximum number of address space identifier (ASID) keys for memory encryption that can be used (one per guest VM).
 - 1st generation of AMD EPYC processors (7xx1) - 15 ASID keys
 - 2nd and 3rd generation (7xx2, 7xx3) - 509 ASID keys (in systems equipped with up to 8TB RAM), 253 ASID keys (in systems equipped with up to 16TB RAM)
 - 4th generation (9xx4) - 1006 ASID keys
- The operating system running in an encrypted virtual machine must contain SEV support.
- SEV-enabled guests pin pages in RAM, preventing any memory overcommit.
- SEV and SEV-ES VMs cannot be compatible with Secure Boot.

Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX) and Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX)

Intel SGX helps protect data in use via application isolation technology. SGX offers hardware-based memory encryption that isolates code and data of a specific application in memory. Intel TDX is a hardware-based trusted execution environment (TEE) that facilitates the deployment of trust domains (TD), which are hardware-isolated virtual machines (VM) designed to protect sensitive data and applications from unauthorized access.

Support for SGX/TDX was released for OpenStack (Train) as a technology preview called [Secured Cloud Management Stack \(SCM\)](#) by Intel. SCM makes modifications to different OpenStack components to achieve the SGX/TDX enablement in different dimensions and capabilities. The SCM modifications are not yet integrated into the official OpenStack releases.

Release v1.0 features (with SGX support):

- Automatic SGX capability inspection and SGX nodes discovery;
- SGX capability enablement in OpenStack;
- SGX VM and BM lifecycle management;
- SGX EPC resource management.

Limitations:

- Intel SGX extensions are available only on subset of Intel CPUs ([list of processors with SGX extensions](#))
- Default Maximum Enclave Page Cache (EPC) Size differs for different CPUs (8-512 GB)

Release v3.0 features (with TDX support):

- Automatic TDX nodes discovery;
- TDX/SGX capability enablement in the same OpenStack platform;
- TDVM guest image customization;
- TDVM instances lifecycle management.

Limitations:

- Intel TDX extensions are only available since 5th generation of Intel Xeon processors ([list of processors compatible with TDX](#))

5.3.2. Support for Confidential Computing in Kubernetes

Confidential Containers (CoCo)

Confidential Containers is an open source community that aims to protect containers and data inside them by leveraging Trusted Execution Environments (TEE). Inside this community, the CNCF Confidential Containers project is the one in charge of the technical implementation of the [proposed architecture](#).

The implementation of Confidential containers supports different technologies like Confidential VMs or Enclave based architectures to create 3 possible scenarios:

- Deploying using VM-based TEEs and the [Kata Containers](#) runtime.
- Deploying using VM-based TEEs by leveraging a peer-pods approach. This relies on Kata Containers remote hypervisor.
- Deploying using the Intel SGX process-based TEE. It relies on the [enclave-cc](#) project.

To enable confidential computing, these scenarios always have to be complemented with the tools and technologies described below:

- Attestation service - To act as a verifier ([RATS architecture](#)) of the evidence provided by the hardware.
- Key Broker Service (KBS) - The KBS is the *Relying Party* that will act as a messenger between the Attester, the Attestation service and the Key Management Service.
- Key management service - A service for securely storing, managing and backing up of cryptographic keys.
- Image build service - Service used to build confidential containers or VM images for end users.
- Image registry - A service that is used to store encrypted and/or signed container and VM images required for CC workloads.

Confidential containers are implemented seamlessly into kubernetes by using the provided Kubernetes operator that will install the required runtime, allowing to quickly set up a confidential containers environment on the cluster. It's also worth mentioning that they can be implemented in an already existing cluster, something to take into consideration when comparing confidential clusters vs confidential containers.

Constellation

Constellation aims to provide a secure and verifiable kubernetes cluster inside of what they call a confidential context. To do so, it relies on encryption, key management, external attestation and verification.

Specifically, it provides the following features

- Runtime encryption: all Kubernetes nodes run inside Confidential VMs (CVMs).
- Network and storage encryption: Constellation augments this with transparent encryption of the network using the Cilium Container Network Interface (CNI) and Wireguard. It also encrypts the persistent storage by relying on the cloud provider (e.g. GCP encrypts volumes at rest by default) or via the dm-crypt and dm-integrity kernel modules.
- Transparent key management: Constellation manages the corresponding cryptographic keys inside CVMs.
- Node attestation and verification: Constellation verifies the integrity of each new CVM-based node using remote attestation based on the TPM 2.0 specification that marks and signs a node based on hardware measurements.

- Confidential computing-optimized images: A node is "good" if it's running a signed Constellation node image (based on a minimal version of Fedora) inside a CVM and is in the expected state.
- "Whole cluster" attestation: provides a single hardware-rooted certificate from which all of the above can be verified.

5.4. COMMERCIAL PROVIDERS

The following are some current large commercial cloud providers in the field, with a confidential computing (CC) offer:

Microsoft Azure

- The services are based on intel SGX and [Open Enclave SDK](#).
- Using the service requires refactoring the applications to make use of the platform-specific SDK, but then the resulting application can be portable over intel, ARM architectures & windows, linux operating systems.

Google Cloud Platform

- The service provides Confidential virtual machines (GCP N2D & C2D VMs) based on AMD SEV and [Asylo](#) technologies.
- The VMs run a shielded operating system with verified OS images. There are different hardware available that give different levels of confidentiality & security to the VMs run on them. [Kubernetes](#) containers are also available.

Amazon Web Services

- The service is based on in-house Nitro enclave technology which provides hardened and constrained virtual machines (no network, no persistent storage, no interactive access).
- This also entails the use of a specific hypervisor and application libraries ([Nitro Enclave SDK](#)).

This list is not exhaustive, and we can expect other companies to follow those leaders and also provide some form of CC in the near future. The smaller ones will certainly not have in-house hardware technologies, but will use available stacks.

The use of commercial cloud providers from different jurisdictions should be studied with great care, as the technical confidentiality of the platforms can be legally undermined in various ways. Also the origin of the data can have sovereignty restrictions that forbid their transit through other countries' infrastructure.

6. ARCHITECTURE DEFINITION

6.1. REQUIREMENT ELICITATION OVERVIEW

Based on the Use Cases analysis via the described methodology, we have grouped their requirements as summarized in [Table 6](#), and then further refined into technical choices for the platform implementation. The description of each requirement is included below. For clarity, we have not included UC3.

Requirements	UC1 epidemiology	UC2 medical imaging	UC4 text anonymization	UC5 demography
Authentication / Users / Access	X	X	X	X
Permissions documentation	X			
Permissions validation (auditable)	X	X	X	X
Data upload, storage	X	X	X	X
Data ingestion (automated)	X			X
Data management (draining)	X			
Data exploration				X
Data anonymization	X	X	X	X
Data anonymity assessment	X		X	X
Audit		X	X	X
Graphical remote access	X	X		
Windows OS access	X			
External web access	X			
GPU accelerators		X	X	
Containers	X	X		
Resource management (quotas)	X		X	
Development management			X	
Install software (researcher)	X	X	X	
Restrict software (administrator)	X		X	
Trusted software repository	X		X	

Requirements	UC1 epidemiology	UC2 medical imaging	UC4 text anonymization	UC5 demography
Vulnerability check	X		X	

Table 6. Use cases requirements summary

Authentication

- Any user will need to be authenticated
- Users will have metadata (contact info, crypto keys, certificates...)
- An administrator can add users
- An administrator can assign users to groups / roles

Access Control

- The owner of a dataset can grant access to users / groups
- The owner of a pipeline can grant access to users / groups
- An administrator can assign resources to users / groups

Audit System

- The owner of a dataset can monitor its accesses
- The owner of a pipeline can monitor its accesses
- Administrators can see platform access
- Administrators can monitor platform use
- Users can set alarms or triggers on resource access

Secure Compute

- **Remote desktop**
 - Access is secured through encrypted network
 - Users can install software (their own or from trusted mirror)
 - Users can use data or results visualization tools
- **Interactive analysis**
 - Users can search data sets
 - Users can choose data sets
 - Users can test computing pipelines
- **Compute API**
 - Can be used by an external workflow system
 - Can be used by an interactive user
- **Compute environment**
 - Provides sandboxing for data sets & computing pipelines
 - Can run pipelines from compute API triggers
 - Attests its own trustworthiness

Secure Storage

- **Encrypted Storage**
 - Data access permissions must have user granularity
 - Different data set can be shared to different users
- **Output Data**
 - Users can download results from the platform
 - Data can be automatically drained (purged)
- **Egress service**
 - Users can automate results publishing if they are allowed to
- **Data ingestion**
 - Users can upload data manually
 - Users can automate data ingestion and update
- **Assisted anonymization**
 - Users can run anonymization tools on a given data set for the parameters introduced and the anonymization model desired (according to the required privacy level and the attacks to be prevented)
 - Users can check anonymization results according to different techniques. He/she can get the anonymization report in different formats, including pdf
 - Users can report the anonymization defects encountered

Development management

- **Code repository**
 - Users can develop computing pipelines code
 - Users can create issues for a pipeline
 - Users can document the pipelines
 - Pipeline code can be checked for Quality Assurance
- **Software mirror**
 - Software is trustable

- Software is signed
- Software is up-to-date
- Software is checked for vulnerabilities

6.2. QUALITY GOALS

SIESTA follows the model defined in the ISO/IEC 25010 standard to define its non-functional requirements and quality goals. Overall, and at a platform level, we consider the following:

Req. ID	Description
RNF-01	Functional Completeness: The system provides functions that cover all of the specified tasks and user objectives.
RNF-02	Availability and maturity: The system is operational, accessible and reliable.
RNF-03	Operability: The system is easy to operate and control by platform operators and resource providers.
RNF-04	Compatibility: The system is compatible with existent technologies, standards and community best practices.
RNF-05	Functional Suitability: The system fulfills the user and operator expectations, in terms of completeness, correctness and appropriateness.
RNF-06	Performance Efficiency: The system only consumes the resources needed, providing appropriate performance for each case.
RNF-07	Confidentiality: Data is only available and accessible to authorized users.
RNF-08	Integrity: The platform will ensure that unauthorized access is now allowed, either to the platform services or to the stored or processed data.
RNF-09	Non-repudiation: The platform should provide methods to prove that a certain action took place.
RNF-10	Accountability: The platform should provide methods to track actions of authorized or unauthorized users.

6.3. STAKEHOLDERS

The used methodology includes a “Personas, EPICs & User Stories” document for each used case that permits to illustrate interactions between several types of person and the SIESTA services. The table below presents the main categories of stakeholder.

Stakeholder	Expectations
Code Reviewer	The code reviewer is a user that wants to verify that the code running on the SIESTA platform can be trusted and to get informed when a code modification may break the data confidentiality and/or integrity.
Data Right Holder	The data right holder wants to copy the data onto the SIESTA platform as easily as possible, but also to be able to check the authorisations associated with the data, and who has accessed the data.

Stakeholder	Expectations
EOSC User	The EOSC user is a scientist willing to analyze sensitive data in the EOSC. It aims at accessing a reliable and trustable solution, where it can run data analysis workflow and retrieve result outputs.
Platform Manager	The platform manager is the person in charge of the scientific platform deployed on the SIESTA infrastructure and providing users with high-level tools. He is looking for a solution that is highly available, secure and whose services are interoperable with those already used in its current developments. It also needs a service for managing the users.
Policy Maker	The policy maker is a non-expert user who has to make technical or political decisions on the basis of results obtained or published on the SIESTA platform. This user expects the platform to be easy to use and to provide trustable results.
Security Officer	The security manager must be able to check that data confidentiality is being respected and have the tools to verify that security policies are being correctly applied.

6.4. COMPONENT OVERVIEW AND SOLUTION STRATEGY

This section describes the technological choices that are made for the initial platform definition. They constitute a starting point for the implementation phase of the project, but some items may evolve in order to adapt to technical, organizational or legal difficulties that may not have been identified at this point of the project.

The services described here will follow a [Technical Readiness Levels](#) (TRL) that will change during the development of the solutions. They will start at low or medium levels and will be provided at high levels for the final stages. All the different services may also not be at the same levels, as that will depend on several factors, not all of which we have control upon, for example, if some services are provided by third parties.

Authentication

Web portal, integrated within something already existing authentication methods:

- [EGI checkin](#)

EGI checkin is already used for all resource providers integrated in the EGI federation, the service is maintained and high-availability is provided.

User data management:

- EGI checkin

Users / Groups / Roles management:

- EGI checkin

Access Control

This mechanism will be handled for each different resource the different services provide. There are no single technology choices to be made.

Audit System

- [Google Trillian](#)
- [BBVA QED](#)

Secure Compute

- **Remote desktop**
 - Cendio ThinLinc (This can be installed on top of a securely configured Linux system, and will leverage all security configurations from the base operating system). Windows operating systems may be required by some use cases.

- **Interactive analysis**

The use cases require the ability to choose and deploy the analysis software by themselves, because they are mainly domain- or data type-specific, and also because some of those tools will be developed or enhanced on the platform.

So the SIESTA platform will not mandate any particular tool and will provide the resources in a way that fulfill the use cases needs.

- **Compute API**

Currently, all service providers are offering an OpenStack environment. This environment is accessible through the OpenStack SDK and OpenStack CLI, which is a well-known API and is directly usable through different languages and tools.

- **Compute environment**

Something that can easily describe infrastructure and provides different backends covering both UC needs and resource providers' services:

- opentofu

That would also enable the platform to target commercial cloud providers, for greater elasticity, interoperability, or enhanced security.

After being provisioned by `opentofu`, to automate the infrastructure configuration and keep it consistent and secure due to reduced user related errors.

- Ansible

To manage secrets for the platform (encryption keys, certificates, etc.)

- Hashicorp Vault
- OpenBao

This service is already provided by IISAS in a [high-availability setup](#) for EGI Federation and is in full production (TRL9).

Secure Storage

- **Encrypted Storage**

This service will be provided as a 2 layer solution, infrastructure as raw storage volumes, by the cloud middleware. Upon which a software encryption layer, that will run inside the secure computing TEE, will provide the data security. This service will use secrets provided by the dedicated service from the secure computing environment.

The technology to do this encryption does not need to be imposed from the platform itself, as a large ecosystem of solutions exists from which each use case can choose.

- **Output Data / Egress service**

Any existing secure data transfer method should be usable, as long as the user is authenticated and authorized to access the relevant data set.

- **Data ingestion**

- Apache Kafka
- OpenSearch / ELK

- **Assisted anonymization**

The appropriate anonymization solution will depend on the source, characteristics and intended use for the data, as well as its structure and features. The service will provide a series of tools covering the use cases of the SIESTA project, while giving room to the incorporation of new or specialized ones (e.g. for medical imaging).

Within WP10, a Python library is under development as the proposed solution for anonymizing structured datasets. This Python library, named *ANJANA*, is open source and provides users with nine anonymization techniques that can be applied to prevent different kinds of attacks that can be carried out on structured and tabular datasets. Concerning this library, for version v.0.2.2 the following links are available:

- Library code (Python), available in GitHub: <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/anjana>.
- Documentation (hosted in ReadTheDocs): <https://anjana.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- Installation using PyPi: <https://pypi.org/project/anjana/>.

In addition, in case users have pre-anonymized data and desire to check its anonymity level across different techniques to identify potential risks or attacks the data may suffer, the use of the Python library *pyCANON* is the proposed solution [8]. *pyCANON* allows users to assess the values of the parameters associated with the same nine anonymization techniques implemented in ANJANA.

Development management

- **Code repository**

Easy-to-use single platform for automated software delivery:

- Gitlab (Community Edition) - installed on Kubernetes enabled infrastructure via GitLab operator

- **Software mirror**

Central repository manager to proxy, collect, and manage the dependencies

- Sonatype Nexus - installed on Kubernetes enabled infrastructure via Nexus operator

Harbor container image repository providing static analysis of vulnerabilities in images through the open source project Trivy

- Harbor with Trivy - installed on Kubernetes enabled infrastructure via Helm charts

6.5. ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAMS

As already indicated, the SIESTA C4 model diagrams are automatically generated using the [Structurizr Domain Specific Language \(DSL\)](#)⁹, with an online and open version of the updated diagrams in the following links:

- Diagrams, in a browseable and online live version: [\[LINK\]](#)¹⁰
- Code (DSL): <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/architecture>

⁹ <https://github.com/structurizr>

¹⁰ <https://structurizr.com/share/94201/c50c8b32-ebb1-4963-a4f0-51193eee0fba>

7. SUMMARY

Our world today is full of data, and a big part of this data is sensitive in terms of personal data, trade secrets or population data among others. In all scientific disciplines, providing researchers with access to as much data as possible will enable them to develop new research topics that will lead to major new discoveries and will empower scientific advances.

A cornerstone of Open Science is the integration of the FAIR principles into the scientific knowledge creation process. However, the nature and sensitivity of the data must be taken into account, following the *“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”* principle. It is important to enable science to work on sensitive data, as easily as possible, without endangering its security and staying within the legal constraints which are imposed by the different applicable regulations.

The SIESTA project will fulfill those requirements as a secure and trusted third party enabler between the sensitive DRHs and the research teams that want to use such data for analytics, developing AI/ML/DL models, statistics purposes, etc.

The technologies needed to achieve such a goal are diverse and some of them quite state of the art, some may still even be at early stages of development. The SIESTA project will explore the different possibilities and means that are available to implement a platform to:

- Deliver trusted cloud-based environments for the analysis of sensitive data, built in a reproducible way, and a set of services to ease the secure sharing through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques
- Enhance the EOSC Exchange services with cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them
- Study, explore and demonstrate the feasibility of FAIR management and processing of sensitive data, showcasing the benefits for society, science and research
- Deliver tools for the secure anonymization or pseudonymisation of datasets, allowing rightholders to safely release sensitive data through the EOSC Exchange
- Provide rights holders with best practices and methodologies for the release of sensitive data following FAIR principles
- Extend the service offer and the capabilities being offered through the EOSC portal, coordinating with the operational and management activities carried out by the EOSC partnership and related projects

After outlining the objectives of the project and this work package, this document sets out the requirements of the various use cases, the technologies available and the targeted architecture. The described architecture is made up of existing services and a set of proven software packages that will be deployed. This work will enable us to respond appropriately to the needs expressed by users and to provide a functional solution with a high TRL.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX I - USE CASE QUESTIONNAIRES

Use case 1 (WP14) "Platform for epidemic data-driven modeling"

I. Introduction

- *Long Name:* **Epidemiology**
- *Short Name:* **Epidemiology**
- *Related WP:* WP14
- *Main contact person:* José J. Ramasco
- *Contact email:* jramasco@ifisc.uib-csic.es
- *Technical contact person:* José J. Ramasco
- *Technical contact email:* jramasco@ifisc.uib-csic.es

Short description of the use case: field, discipline, community

The use case 1 focusses on computational epidemiology.

II. Use case description

1. Presentation

The use case objectives are:

- To collect data required for epidemiological models (population, mobility, surveillance, etc.) from standard sources public and private.
- To develop the tools to share participatory surveillance systems data within the SIESTA framework.
- To build the models needed to study propagation scenarios of generic infectious diseases using these data.
- To develop a user-friendly interface that will allow the access of expert and non-expert users to the models.

The partners participating in the WP14 are: CSIC (leading), ISI, Inserm, INE and Javier de la Cueva.

2. Expectations within the SIESTA project

The objective of the WP14 is to develop an ecosystem in the SIESTA platform, and by extension in EOSC, able to use data to perform computational epidemic predictions. For this, we will need to build synthetic populations for France, Italy and Spain and to develop models versatile enough for external users to define the particular epidemic process that they want to analyze. What we expect from SIESTA is to have a hosting platform, which can manage the access of users, the environment in which the models can run and the safe sharing of the results with the corresponding user.

III. Technical description

1. Community management

We are not currently using any authentication/authorization system. This is something that must be provided by the SIESTA platform, not by the use case directly. The tools that we are planning to develop are open, there is no special restriction of access except for the fact that each user must see only his/her own simulations and results. Our software will be based on Python and C++, it does not need any special requirements to run. A standard linux-like installation in a technical or scientific environment is enough.

2. Analysis pipelines

The data is being searched and downloaded by the different partners in local. These data will form the basis for the synthetic populations and of the population models, which will be the only data that will be needed to upload to the platform along with the software for simulations. The basic data will be updated as the demographic data is updated with certain regularity, but this can once per year or even less frequent.

3. Data staging and compute platform

The optimal structure will contain a docker to maintain the data and the software. The simulation tools can be demanding, but they will be adapted to generic CPUs in a linux environment. The software will be accessed through a graphical system that can run in general browsers. Once the users have defined the epidemic models, the output will be shown graphically in a very limited set of variables and the results will be downloadable in a compressed csv format. Every user must be able to see his/her previous simulations, to download at least the model definition in a json format (few kbs) and also the results of his/her last simulation.

4. Trusted computing

Once the user management is defined for the general platform, we have very little add. There is no special requirement on the users of WP14, since the capabilities that they will have are limited and they do not affect to sensitive data. Our data falls mainly under the category DL2, it is based on open data DL1 but the owners request the download from their own web pages.

IV. Data description

In this section, we will provide a description of the data used for the project, classifying it by data type and, at the same time, describing the sensitivity and access controls for each of these types.

The data consulted for this specific use case is primarily intended to be used to generate synthetic populations for input into the corresponding epidemiological models. Most of these data sources are publicly and freely accessible, but they have the restriction that they cannot be stored in third-party data containers for sharing with others. Therefore, these data will not be directly stored on our platform; instead, we will directly store the synthetic populations generated from them. Storing only these synthetic data implies that no personal data is stored, thus avoiding data privacy issues. The main challenge to address is the possibility of de-anonymization in cases where we work with very small population kernels. When generating a population with distributions of characteristics similar to real ones, we could almost exactly replicate the data of the real population for cases with few inhabitants. Therefore, restrictions such as applying minimum population thresholds need to be implemented.

Among the types of data used, we have the following:

- Places and locations
- Households
- Habits
- Work
- Population

The majority of the collected data comes from **the public agencies responsible for the general coordination of statistical services**

Sources:

- <https://esploradati.istat.it/databrowser/#/>
- <https://www.insee.fr/fr/accueil>
- <https://www.ine.es/>

Places and locations

The data contains cadastral information providing insights into the locations of various types of buildings (residential and other uses), whether they are public (schools, hospitals) or private (restaurants, offices, leisure, among others), as well as statistical data allowing us to determine the number of buildings designated for each type of use, segmented by population centers. This type of data has a sensitivity level of DLS1 according to the Data Sensitivity Levels Table. It is considered heavy data as it contains information about all buildings nationwide, and the records include geographic information, a field that is heavy and stored in specific formats for this type of data, such as Shapefiles or GeoJSON.

Additionally, these data include information regarding mobility between subregions, which serves to assign destination zones for the population (where they work, engage in other activities) based on their area of origin, which may or may not coincide with their destination zone.

Sources:

- <https://cadastre.data.gouv.fr/>
- <https://www.catastro.minhap.es/webinspire/index.html>
- <https://catastomappe.it/mappa>
- <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

Households

The data contains statistical information about various characteristics of the population, such as the distributions of households by the number of occupants and by the type of family units (with or without children). All this data is presented in the form of estimated absolute numbers and is non-de-anonymizable as it does not contain any personal data. It is stratified by municipality, but data for very small populations are excluded to prevent de-anonymization for small samples.

Habits

The data includes information about the daily movements made by the population in the form of trips classified by destination type (work, home, shopping, etc.), as well as distributions of the time allocated by the population for each of these types of activities.

Work

The public agencies responsible for the general coordination of statistical services in each country provide us with data that allows us to understand how the population is distributed, classifying it according to various variables such as:

- Type of occupation (students, employed, retired, unemployed, etc.)
- Type of work schedule (full-time, part-time, split-shift, etc.)
- Sector where workers are employed
- Number of employees by type of institution or job position (education, healthcare personnel, etc.)

Population

We obtain populations divided by characteristics such as municipality or age groups from sources such as the official censuses of each country.

1. Input Data

Data sources

In this section, we will describe the input data stored in our platform for conducting epidemiological simulations.

From the datasets outlined in the previous subsection, we generate a synthetic population for each country to be analyzed. This population is entirely synthetic and does not contain any real personal data. For the agents included in these populations, in addition to assigning them a series of general characteristics such as age, gender, or municipality of origin, which follow a distribution very similar to that found in the real population of each country, we also assign them a series of characteristics that will determine their behavior once we conduct the simulations. Among these characteristics are:

- Origin subregion and destination subregion: in these two areas, the agents will carry out most of their daily activities.
- Job position and building where the work is performed.
- Household
- Number of trips per day and mode of transportation used for these trips
- Type of activities carried out during each day (shopping, dining out, leisure activities, visits to medical centers, etc.), as well as the most likely places to be visited of each type based on their regions of origin and destination.

It is estimated that the storage size required for synthetic populations, as well as information related to buildings, will be on the order of gigabytes.

Once we have the synthetic population files ready to be included in the platform, the inputs we will have in it to perform the simulations will be as follows:

- **Files with agent information.** These will be in .csv or similar format and will contain the characteristics of each agent. Each agent will be a record, and each characteristic will be an attribute, with numerical and string attributes.
- **Files with building and housing information.** These will be in a geographic format such as Shapefile or GeoJSON and will contain relevant information about each building, such as its geolocation, use, capacity, and area. These attributes are crucial in determining agent behavior within them and the probability of contagion if contacts occur.

All data will be updated periodically based on the update frequency of the various consulted sources. We work with both static data (surveys conducted at specific points in time) and dynamic data, such as cadastral data or census data from each country.

Data uses

The first step is to program the automatic download of data from the sources mentioned in the previous subsection, using Python as the programming tool and leveraging its specific libraries such as BeautifulSoup, Scrapy, or Selenium for this task.

Once the data is downloaded, we perform a statistical analysis based on the data and microdata collected, as mentioned in the previous subsection. For this analysis, we also program in Python using specific libraries for statistical analysis such as NumPy, SciPy, or Pandas, among others.

All preliminary operations will be primarily conducted using the VS Code editor, a versatile and free tool that can be used across multiple operating systems, including Windows, macOS, and Linux.

When working with geographic data, we will carry out the necessary preliminary analyses using the QGIS tool. For subsequent processing of this data, we will again use Python, utilizing specific libraries for working with geographic data such as GeoPandas.

Privacy / confidentiality

As mentioned in previous sections, the data included in the platform will not contain any real personal data. The only real data included will pertain to geolocations and building usage types, which are freely accessible through third-party sources.

We must consider that, although this data is freely accessible, it is not permitted to be shared directly on third-party platforms. Therefore, we cannot include it directly on our platform.

The data from the consulted public institutions typically come in aggregated form by default in most cases.

2. Output Data

Data Sharing

The user will receive two main outputs:

- A file containing the parameterization entered by the user to conduct the simulations will be provided. This file will allow the user to compare results from different executions as well as to rerun simulations with parameterizations previously defined and used.
- A set of files containing the results obtained from the simulations will be provided, including data about the evolution of infections. These data will include information about individuals in each disease state at each stage of the simulation (the duration of each stage is entered by the user), as well as data about the disease progression such as incidence or prevalence. Infection data will be returned divided by different attributes such as building type, subregion, among others.

The user will not have direct access from the platform to the data used to construct the synthetic populations, nor to these synthetic populations themselves; they will only have access to the results of applying simulations on them. Due to this approach, we will not be involved in privacy issues by directly sharing any type of personal data. The results will only contain aggregated data, and under no circumstances will access be granted to the input data or the synthetic populations used unless explicitly requested and permission is given for the specific case.

Use case 2 (WP15) “Medical (Neuro)Imaging”

I. Introduction

- *Long Name:* **Medical neuroimaging**
- *Short Name:* **Medical**
- *Related WP:* WP15
- *Main contact person:* Robert Oostenveld
- *Contact email:* robert.oostenveld@donders.ru.nl
- *Technical contact person:* idem
- *Technical contact email:* idem

Short description of the use case: field, discipline, community

The use case 2 focusses on computational research on medical data. To make it specific, we specialize in human neuroimaging for which data analysis is used to understand the functioning of the brain in relation to disease, cognition, and development.

Neuroimaging is conducted in research institutes using techniques shared with hospitals, such as MRI, EEG and MEG. Besides recordings of brain structure and function, health/clinical/genetic data can be collected, but also data in relation to cognitive and/or behavioral tasks, and demographic data that relates to health and/or development.

Human neuroimaging, sometimes also referred to as brain mapping (see <https://www.humanbrainmapping.org/>), is part of the larger field of Neuroscience (see for example <https://www.sfn.org/>), which also covers molecular, cellular, animal, theoretical, and computational research. Neuroimaging overlaps with cognitive, social and behavioral research. Neuroimaging research tends to be very interdisciplinary, with trained neuroscientists working together with psychologists, physicists, linguists, computer scientists, doctors, mathematicians, and researchers trained in other domains.

II. Use case description

1. Presentation

An introductory section describing the use case in general terms (objectives, means, partners, etc.)

The objective of Use Case 2 is to contribute to the SIESTA project delivering solutions that can be used for Medical neuroimaging research. As SIESTA is about a secure interactive cloud environment, we focus on how to process personal data which is commonly (but not always) the case. Furthermore, neuroimaging often involves large and hence computationally intense datasets.

We will not collect new datasets (that would be too time-consuming and expensive) but will select representative existing open-access datasets from public sources as demonstrators of our use case. This allows processing these datasets in the SIESTA environment, even during development when the SIESTA environment is not yet completely secure. Although these datasets are public, the characteristics are similar to data that is recorded in medical neuroimaging where the data cannot be shared.

Our goal is to describe (1) input and (2) output staging and provide (3) anonymization procedures that render data usable in terms of data structure and relevant features to develop and test (4) pipeline examples. The outputs of pipelines on anonymized data may be biologically irrelevant but are good enough for testing. Computation can then be executed 'securely' on the original personal data and output delivered to users.

WP15 is mainly implemented by researchers from the SRU (Nijmegen, NL), NRU (Copenhagen, DK) and CNRS (Toulouse, FR). The specific neuroimaging partners in the SIESTA project have more methodological and technical expertise than the typical neuroimaging researcher, but we know our local non-SIESTA colleagues at our respective home institutions well: those are conceived as the future users of the SIESTA platform.

2. Expectations within the SIESTA project

What do you think could be your main objectives to be achieved within the SIESTA project in relation to this Use Case? What do you think you will be able to do after the project that you could not now? Please try to identify what are the requirements that could make a difference on this Use Case at technical level and that are not solved by now.

The style of working that we consider is schematically depicted in <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/blob/main/README.md>

A data owner should be able to upload a dataset composed of sensitive and personal data from many research participants to the secure environment, knowing that a researcher performing computations on that data will not be able to identify any of the individual participants from the said dataset. If the data cannot be directly accessed, and none of the individuals whose data is part of the dataset can be identified from the results, then the results are anonymous and GDPR does not apply.

A researcher should be able to log in, install software plus requirements, and design and run an interactive analysis to set up an analysis without being able to extract personal details from the shared dataset. Said analysis is subsequently executed on the actual/original dataset. Results from the analysis are shared with the researcher, but only if it can be established that those are anonymous (and hence GDPR again does not apply).

Right now the most commonly used approach to reuse data in the field of neuroimaging is for the data owner to share the data (e.g., by having a researcher download it) which means that the data owner cannot control what the researcher will do with the data. Since the data owner cannot control the use of the data, they are hesitant and will not share sensitive personal data¹¹. As there is no access to the data, the researcher cannot do the analysis. An enclave offers a potential solution but is not the aim of SIESTA. What we envision is that SIESTA will implement a "militarized zone" where the original data is secure, and a "demilitarized zone" where the interaction with the analysis pipeline and with pseudodata can happen. Once the pipeline is ready, it is executed in the militarized

¹¹ or sharing requires long legal and contractual discussions between both parties, where ethical constraints (limitations in the informed consent) also apply.

zone on the real data, results are checked for anonymity and transferred to the demilitarized zone where the researcher can access them.

III. Technical description

1. Community management

Which tools are you using for authentication/authorization? Do you have a specific procedure for accepting new members into your community? If you are using different tools, how are they interacting with each other? Should anonymous access be authorized?

Microsoft365 (separate per organization), [ORCID](#), federated IdPs like [SURFconext](#) and [WAYF](#).

The principle of data minimization implies that we should not collect information from the platform users that is not needed. If the system is really secure to process sensitive data, there is no risk for a data breach and a Data Use Agreement or License other than CC0 might not be required. Of course the data provider might require otherwise. However, if for a certain dataset there is no legal agreement needed to compute anonymous derived data, there is also no justification (under the GDPR) for SIESTA to always collect personal information from the users of the system.

Authentication of SIESTA users that perform computations is needed to differentiate users so that one user can access their own intermediate pipelines and data, but not that of others.

Therefore the WP15 don't see legal reasons why computations that result in anonymous data would require a person to identify themselves. However, I can imagine practical constraints that require researchers to identify themselves when using the SIESTA compute platform. For example to determine eligibility to use the EOSC facilities, or to deal with the costs of storage and compute facilities.

This is also valid for data users. Since the idea is that users access anonymized data to interactively develop a pipeline, there is no need for a secure login. Data controllers who upload data should be fully identified (for the sake of the SIESTA platform) and agreed on how their data will be used.

2. Analysis pipelines

Describe the flow of data from local resources (i.e. user laptop) to the infrastructure, from one infrastructure to another. Do you need a multi-site federation? Do you regularly need to transfer data among distributed datacenters? Is there a workflow controlled by experts in the community that regulates the needed data management or every users can make DM requests?

Data goes from the data controller institute to the platform and is never touched by the platform users. Software and dependencies get installed over the internet. Code goes from the user/researcher's personal computer to the platform and is further developed locally on pseudodata. It is then run by SIESTA on the real data. Results go from the platform to the researcher's personal computer.

Not sure what is meant with distributed datacenters... Like big tech where they distribute their ICT infrastructure over multiple datacenters (aka buildings in different cities)? I think it is to be phrased as the “IT environment of the data owner” and the “IT environment of the researcher” and the “SIESTA environment”. A nice-to-have option is for SIESTA to access the data from the data controller infrastructure directly and is cloned only when needed.

The WP15 doesn't see that external experts will be involved, other than the data controller/owner, the researcher, and the specialists that host the SIESTA platform.

There will not be a “community that regulates workflows”.

The WP15 is not sure whether we have matching expectations regarding the “data management” that is to be done and by whom. In our view there is a split between the data controller/owner (only manages the input data and reviews the output data) and the researcher (only manages the computations and receives the output data, interprets that and makes that FAIR).

3. Data staging and compute platform

This section details the tasks that will need to be carried out on the SIESTA secure platform, as well as the requirements of the use case in relation to this platform. For example, do you need a graphical / interactive interface to the compute platform or specific hardware resources like NPU, GPU, FPGA accelerators. What applications are you planning to use? Which operating systems do you need on the secure platform (Linux, Windows). Do you need a container runtime (e.g. docker). These requirements are not only technical, but also organizational and legal (for example, the software should only be accessed by a specific user / group).

Yes, SIESTA is explicitly about an interactive environment. The interaction that we have in mind is the researcher using a terminal, text editor, and/or visual programming and analysis tools that run in a (virtual) desktop environment. For example a VNC session using [Guacamole](#).

Users should be able to install software as needed to develop an analysis pipeline, which can include containerized applications, but is often not the case.

4. Trusted computing

In your case, can you describe what you expect from a trusted computing platform? What services are you looking for that are not yet available? What services are you already using that you would like to keep using on the secure platform?

In the medical imaging use case we are not considering [Trusted Computing](#). The computations on the personal data are anticipated to run on a partition of the cloud compute environment that can architecturally be completely separated from the partition on which the researchers interact, hence we don't see the need to implement this at the hardware level.

IV. Data description

In this section, each kind of data (input, output) that will be processed or stored on the SIESTA infrastructure should be described. If you have a Data Management Plan (DMP) you can reuse parts of it to provide answers. Specific elements for input or output data are also listed in the dedicated sections.

The following items should be covered for each kind of data:

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*
- *Legal constraints (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)*
- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted? Is an encryption management service needed? Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others (DMP: 3.2.2.2)*
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*

As we cannot trust SIESTA prototypes yet, in WP15 we will only demonstrate use cases using publicly shared open-access data. This data is not ours, but is shared by others in line with their legal and ethical requirements. We will not produce new or derived data (other than temporarily for demonstration purposes inside the SIESTA platform) that we will distribute.

Actual data used in WP15 is DSL 1 and 2, and potentially DSL 3. The Use Case aims to specify functional requirements for data at DSL 4 to 6.

We have not discussed in WP15 yet whether access to the SIESTA is to be granted to an individual researcher or a research team. If it were to a research team, we have not yet discussed what the different roles and responsibilities of team members are. At this moment we are implementing example analyses that are run by a single researcher (or if you want: a team that consists of a single person).

Since the data is “sensitive and personal”, we assume that the data owner falls outside the research team (i.e., the person or persons that define the research question for which the data can provide an answer). If the owner were part of the research team, we don’t see the issue in using a central cloud compute platform or the need for SIESTA. Partners in WP15 are all on a daily basis already analyzing personal data that is collected by their respective team members, on the respective team’s compute platform (which can be an encrypted laptop as part of that platform).

1. Input Data

Data sources

- *What is the origin or the provenance of the dataset? (DMP: 1.1.8)*
- *What are the types of the collected data (images, numbers, text, ...)? (DMP: 1.1.4 & 1.1.5)*
- *Which data formats are used? Is there any specification/standard?*
- *Is there any metadata associated with the data?*
- *Where is the data (if any) currently stored (type of storage)?*
- *What is the expected size (GiB, TB)? (DMP: 1.1.6)*
- *How frequently is data updated?*
- *At which rate is the data collected (e.g. 100GiB/year)?*
- *How much storage may be required for the duration of the project?*
- *How and when (if data access scheduling is required) can the data be accessed? (DMP: few questions in section 3.2)*
- *Are there established de-identification/anonymization methods for these data formats? Are they recognised standards/community best practices? Have you applied any of them beforehand?*

Most of these are documented in the DMP and on GitHub on <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15>. More specific questions are welcome here.

Data uses

- *What types of analysis are you planning to perform on these data (statistical, image processing, etc.)?*
- *What type of software do you use for analyzing your data?*
- *Will you use AI methods?*
 - *If yes: Do you want to run it in the cloud?*
 - *Should the inference run on a single computer?*
 - *How much memory does the training require?*
- *Do you need hardware accelerators? (e.g. GPU, FPGA, NPU)*
- *Are there any constraints for those accelerators:*
 - *Quantity (for the whole platform, per VM, etc.)*
 - *Memory (is there a minimum required)*
 - *type/brand/model/API requirements*
- *What deep learning framework is used (Tensorflow, PyTorch, etc), if any?*
- *What tools are used during experimentation (e.g. JupyterLab, PyCharm, VScode)?*

Most of these are documented in the DMP and on GitHub on <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15>. More specific questions are welcome here.

Privacy / confidentiality

- *Does the described dataset / output contain personal data? (DMP: 6.1.3)*
- *Are you going to use confidential proprietary data, or have other access restrictions you would like to enforce?*
- *Is this going to be actual or simulated data? If the latter, how was the data created?*
- *Are you using previously anonymised data? How and by whom was the data anonymised?*

- *Can data be transferred to a third-party cloud? Can the data be transferred across borders inside the EEA?*
- *Is there associated metadata that raises any privacy concerns?*
- *Do you need to augment data for training purposes?*
- *Any other information governance restrictions from the data controller or authorities that should be taken into account?*

I hope this is mostly clear from the DMP and the explanations above. Please look at <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15> and come with specific questions.

2. Output Data

Data Sharing

The overall objective is to enhance the EOSC Exchange services by delivering a set of cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC, demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them. In this context it has to be explained how the data can be shared:

- *Are you planning to share your data with other researchers after the analysis?*
- *Are you planning to share aggregated statistics concerning your data? Do you need to apply additional privacy techniques before sharing these statistics (e.g. differential privacy)?*
- *Would you like to publicly release the analyzed/transformed resulting data?*
- *What are your requirements regarding the privacy-usefulness trade-off?*
- *Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?*

I hope this is mostly clear from the DMP and the explanations above. Please look at <https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15> and come with specific questions.

Use case 4 (WP17) “Text Anonymization on Sensitive Data”

I. Introduction

- **Long Name:** Text anonymization on sensitive data
- **Short Name:** Text anonymization
- **Related WP:** WP17
- **Main contact person:** Víctor González Castro; Laura Fernández Robles
- **Contact email:** victor.gonzalez@unileon.es; l.fernandez@unileon.es
- **Technical contact person:** Víctor González Castro; Laura Fernández Robles
- **Technical contact email:** victor.gonzalez@unileon.es; l.fernandez@unileon.es

Short description of the use case: field, discipline, community

This use case aims to anonymize unstructured texts with sensitive data, so that these can be disclosed for research purposes. In our case, the research purpose would be to train a text classification model to ease the preliminary treatment of these documents (e.g., a CERT might need to make a first classification of written reports with cyber incidents depending on the type of incident prior to their analysis).

II. Use case description

1. Presentation

An introductory section describing the use case in general terms (objectives, means, partners, etc.)

The main objective of this Use Case is to develop a solution for anonymisation or pseudonymization consisting of finding sensitive data in unstructured texts. The topic of the texts makes them unable to be disclosed by the authorities, so data is not available to work with it on this WP. Therefore, a dataset with sensitive data should be generated synthetically. This Use case will be developed within WP17, lead by ULE (18PM) and whose partners are JdIC (1PM) and CSIC (2 PMs)

2. Expectations within the SIESTA project

What do you think could be your main objectives to be achieved within the SIESTA project in relation to this Use Case? What do you think you will be able to do after the project that you could not now? Please try to identify what are the requirements that could make a difference on this Use Case at technical level and that are not solved by now.

The objectives of this WP17 written in the project proposal and in the Grant Agreement are:

- To create a synthetic dataset of text documents simulating National Centre for Missing and Exploited Children (NCMEC) reports about Child Sexual Exploitation Material (CSEM) since, due to the sensitive nature of the real data, a real dataset is not available. This dataset will be annotated so that (a) the personal data is localized and categorized into types and (b) the document has a label indicating

its type (e.g., containing different types of CSE, other activities of CSE, no CSE, etc.).

- To develop a solution for data anonymisation and pseudonymisation consisting on finding the sensitive data in the text, by means of Named Entity Recognition (NER).

The topic of the first one (i.e. CSEM) might have to be changed, as it is not possible to gather enough unstructured text reports to fine-tune a generative model (e.g., a LLM) to generate a synthetic dataset. Anyway, the topic of the reports, i.e., cyber incident reports, will be still within the cybercrime prevention domain and, thus, real data cannot be disclosed for research purposes in general terms.

One of the main issues we face when trying to get real reports is that the authorities cannot give us access, so we cannot use them in our experiments. A reliable anonymization tool in unstructured texts that could produce anonymized texts useful for text classification would certainly make a difference so that we would have access to real data. In addition, this anonymization tool should cope with different languages, and cope with entities that are not known in advance, thus requiring knowledge generalization or disambiguation.

III. Technical description

1. Community management

Which tools are you using for authentication/authorization? Do you have a specific procedure for accepting new members into your community? If you are using different tools, how are they interacting with each other? Should anonymous access be authorized?

Not sure about this. Maybe it could be answered in the Persona-User stories' document...

2. Analysis pipelines

Describe the flow of data from local resources (i.e. user laptop) to the infrastructure, from one infrastructure to another. Do you need a multi-site federation? Do you regularly need to transfer data among distributed datacenters? Is there a workflow controlled by experts in the community that regulates the needed data management or every users can make DM requests?

In an ideal scenario, the authority that holds the real sensitive unstructured text (i.e. cyber incident reports but could be any other reports such as police reports, CSEM reports) would access the SIESTA platform from their local resources, transfer the data to the SIESTA server(s), where the anonymization would take place. Both the original and the anonymised texts can be stored on the SIESTA platform, although only the authority that owns the original texts would have access to them.

Thereafter, researchers could access the SIESTA platform to, depending on the permissions that the authority that owns the original data:

1. Download the anonymized texts as if they accessed a data repository, or

2. Train a text classification model on the SIESTA platform and run experiments with it on the anonymised texts. This model will be stored in SIESTA, in an appropriate format.

Finally, the authority can access the SIESTA platform to either download the model or to run it on the SIESTA platform, on their original data.

The authority would probably like to control and regulate which researchers would have access to the anonymised texts (e.g., only researchers they have signed an agreement/contract/project with).

3. Data staging and compute platform

This section details the tasks that will need to be carried out on the SIESTA secure platform, as well as the requirements of the use case in relation to this platform. For example, do you need a graphical / interactive interface to the compute platform or specific hardware resources like NPU, GPU, FPGA accelerators. What applications are you planning to use? Which operating systems do you need on the secure platform (Linux, Windows). Do you need a container runtime (e.g. docker). These requirements are not only technical, but also organizational and legal (for example, the software should only be accessed by a specific user / group).

To accomplish the tasks laid out in the analysis pipeline, the only hardware requirements would be GPU(s) to be able to train/execute deep learning models to classify texts. In terms of software, the OS required would be Linux and a server that would allow users to run experiments written in Python (e.g., Jupyter notebooks). In any case, the user should be able to change the Python version and install specific packages if required.

4. Trusted computing

In your case, can you describe what you expect from a trusted computing platform? What services are you looking for that are not yet available? What services are you already using that you would like to keep using on the secure platform?

IV. Data description

In this section, each kind of data (input, output) that will be processed or stored on the SIESTA infrastructure should be described. If you have a Data Management Plan (DMP) you can reuse parts of it to provide answers. Specific elements for input or output data are also listed in the dedicated sections.

The following items should be covered for each kind of data:

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
The data will consist of cyber incident reports issued by particulars or organizations to institutions that deal with cyber incidents (e.g. CERTs). These data may contain personal data and confidential information that should not be disclosed. Therefore, the sensitivity level should be DSL4. With respect to the ethical aspects, we will use data corresponding to real cyber incidents which have

been made publicly available¹². We will either use them as they are or generate synthetic data by fine-tuning a generative model. In any case, the ethical or legal issues should not be high, as either the data have been disclosed, or would be simulated.

- **Data access** (DMP: Section 3.2): With respect to the dataset to be used in the Use Case, we will explore the option of storing the dataset in OpenCAYLE (<https://www.scayle.es/opencayle/>) - or any other, depending on the requirements of the SIESTA project - and we would provide public access to both the dataset and the annotations. With respect to the data stored on the SIESTA platform, the data access depends on who the owner of the data gives access permission to (e.g. only to the anonymized reports, to the original reports, etc.).
- **Data size** (DMP: Q 1.1.6): The expected size of the dataset should not exceed 5 GiB.

- **Legal constraints** (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)

The data we will use in our Use Case, we will use data corresponding to real cyberincidents which have been made publicly available, and as long as we can amend the GA, it should not be related to Child Sexual Abuse (as it is not being possible to generate a dataset due to lack of textual reports to train a generative model). We will either use them as they are or generate synthetic data by fine-tuning a generative model. In any case, the ethical or legal issues should not be high, as either the data have been disclosed, or would be simulated.

As for the data that would be used in the real scenario, the cybersecurity organization (e.g. CERTs) would own the data, so the data should only be disclosed when and with whom they agree to it, probably after signing an appropriate NDA, and after appropriate anonymization.

- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted? Is an encryption management service needed? Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*

Probably, if the legal constraints would require it, the data should be encrypted.

- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*

- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others* (DMP: 3.2.2.2)

The dataset used in this use case can be open for research purposes.

If we talk about the real data that would be used by organizations, they would want this data to be restricted only to people allowed to analyze it, prior to the reports' anonymization.

- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*

In the real case scenario, permissions should be set to single users or to multiple users. I foresee two different roles:

¹² The data has been gathered from websites such as the [European Repository of Cyberincidents](#), [Cyberoperations tracker](#) of the Council of Foreign Relations, [ICANN cybersecurity incident log](#), [CSIS significant cyberincidents](#), or the [University of Maryland CISSM Cyberattacks database](#)

1. Researchers with limited access to the data (i.e. those researchers that can access only the anonymised data for analyzing it or using it to train classification models), and
 2. Users with full access to the data (i.e. to the non-anonymised data), to whom the stakeholders (i.e. the organizations that have stored the cybersecurity reports) have granted such permission.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
Logs to control who accesses each data, and when should be recorded.

1. Input Data

Data sources

- *What is the origin or the provenance of the dataset?* (DMP: 1.1.8)
The dataset has been gathered from websites that have left reports available for research purposes. These reports will be used directly, but can also be used to generate synthetic data in the context of the SIESTA project.
- *What are the types of the collected data (images, numbers, text, ...)?* (DMP: 1.1.4 & 1.1.5)
The data consists of unstructured text reports, which have not been previously preprocessed (either if we used the original data or generate synthetic data): it will be raw, unstructured text. Therefore, it can be considered primary, as it will be made available without any preprocessing (apart from the annotations).
- *Which data formats are used? Is there any specification/standard?*
All these reports (along with the annotations made to them, e.g. report type, data that should be anonymised) will be stored in either a single csv file or in json files (i.e. one per report)
- *Is there any metadata associated with the data?*
The type of cyber incident the report contains and the entities that should be anonymised and their location
- *Where is the data (if any) currently stored (type of storage)?*
The University of León's institutional email is managed by Google, and, therefore, professors and researchers have an institutional Google Drive account. We are currently storing the data in such account.
- *What is the expected size (GiB, TB)?* (DMP: 1.1.6)
The expected size of the dataset should not exceed the order of GiB (specifically, less than 5 GiB).
- *How frequently is data updated?*
The dataset we will use in the use case prototype of this project will not be regularly updated, i.e. it may have updates but not necessarily periodic.
With respect to the data in the real use of this application, as there are cyber incidents every day, the data may be updated daily, weekly or monthly. It depends on the use the cybersecurity institutions made of the platform: for instance, if they only use it to share data securely with researchers, they may update it every month (i.e. providing the reports of each month). If they use the platform as a databank for their data, it may be updated in a daily basis.
- *At which rate is the data collected (e.g. 100GiB/year)?*
Not sure about that, but it should be in the order of a few GiB per year.
- *How much storage may be required for the duration of the project?*

For the duration of the project, i.e., for the prototyping of the use case, not more than 10 GiB per year (taking into account both the data and the DL models to anonymize and classify it).

- *How and when (if data access scheduling is required) can the data be accessed?* (DMP: few questions in section 3.2)

There is no specific scheduling for accessing the data

- *Are there established de-identification/anonymisation methods for these data formats? Are they recognised standards/community best practices? Have you applied any of them beforehand?*

There are some research papers that use anonymisation methods based on Named Entity Recognition. So far we have used NER to detect entities, but not yet to de-identify or anonymise them.

Data uses

- *What types of analysis are you planning to perform on these data (statistical, image processing, etc.)?*

Natural Language Processing (NLP), both for detect/de-identify/anonymise the appropriate entities, and to classify the anonymised reports.

- *What type of software do you use for analyzing your data?*

We use software developed in-house, consisting on Python scripts that use the usual NLP/ Machine Learning / Deep Learning libraries (e.g. NLTK, spaCy, Tensorflow, Pytorch, etc.)

- *Will you use AI methods?*

- *If yes: Do you want to run it in the cloud?* Yes. For the work on the SIESTA project, we do not need to run the AI methods in the cloud, although they are part of this use case (i.e. the anonymization will be based on Deep Learning), so they will be needed to be run in the cloud.

- *Should the inference run on a single computer?* Yes, provided that the computer has a GPU for running Deep Learning models.

- *How much memory does the training require?* Similar tasks to the ones we want to carry out in our use case were done on a machine with the following specifications: 128 GB of RAM, two processors Intel Xeon E5-2630v3 of 2,4GHz and two Nvidia Titan Xp. The GPU memory was 40GB

- *Do you need hardware accelerators? (e.g. GPU, FPGA, NPU)*

Yes, GPU to allow Deep Learning models to work properly

- *Are there any constraints for those accelerators:*

- *Quantity (for the whole platform, per VM, etc.)*
- *Memory (is there a minimum required)*
- *type/brand/model/API requirements*

- *What deep learning framework is used (Tensorflow, PyTorch, etc), if any?*

- *What tools are used during experimentation (e.g. JupyterLab, PyCharm, VScode)?* During the experimentation we use either PyCharm or Spyder. For the use case, the users can also use JupyterLab if accessing through a web browser, or they can use PyCharm, if accessing through some sort of remote desktop.

Privacy / confidentiality

- *Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?* (DMP: 6.1.3)

The dataset consists of data obtained from reports made available on the Internet. They might contain personal data. However, as they are publicly available, we assume that they have been allowed to disclose it.

In case we create more reports synthetically, the personal data (i.e., names, addresses, IP addresses, etc.) of these texts would be simulated, so no real personal data would be contained in them

- *Are you going to use confidential proprietary data, or have other access restrictions you would like to enforce?*

The data is publicly available, so in principle, we do not need to enforce any restrictions.

- *Is this going to be actual or simulated data? If the latter, how was the data created?*

The dataset will be actual data publicly available on the Internet. However, we may also use synthetic data, which would be created by fine-tuning a generative model (e.g. a LLM) with such data to generate more cyber incident reports.

- *Are you using previously anonymised data? How and by whom was the data anonymised?*

The reports are not anonymised. We plan to annotate them manually or semi-manually. This could be done by a person we would hire to be part of our labeling team for this purpose.

- *Can data be transferred to a third-party cloud? Can the data be transferred across borders inside the EEA?*

The data we are using while the SIESTA project takes place can be transferred to third-party clouds and within borders inside the EEA. The real data that would be used once the SIESTA platform is working may not be transferable (depending on the nature of the data and the requirements of the stakeholder).

- *Is there associated metadata that raises any privacy concerns?*

No, as far as we are aware.

- *Do you need to augment data for training purposes?*

We may need to create synthetic cyber incident reports, as specified above

- *Any other information governance restrictions from the data controller or authorities that should be taken into account?*

No, as far as we are aware.

2. Output Data

Data Sharing

The overall objective is to enhance the EOSC Exchange services by delivering a set of cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC, demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them. In this context it has to be explained how the data can be shared:

- *Are you planning to share your data with other researchers after the analysis?*

We would like to make publicly available for research purposes the cyber incident reports dataset with the labels of the type of report and the anonymisable entities' annotations.

- *Are you planning to share aggregated statistics concerning your data? Do you need to apply additional privacy techniques before sharing these statistics (e.g. differential privacy)?*

We are not planning to share aggregated statistics concerning this dataset

- *Would you like to publicly release the analyzed/transformed resulting data?*

Yes, we would like to publicly release the anonymised dataset.

- *What are your requirements regarding the privacy-usefulness trade-off?*

We have no specific requirements concerning this, since the data we have gathered is already available on the Internet, and some other data will be synthetic, and we have no concerns sharing the annotations we will make.

- *Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?*

None, as far as we are aware.

Use case 5 (WP18) “Demography”

I. Introduction

- *Long Name:* **Demographics**
- *Short Name:* **Demographics**
- *Related WP:* WP18
- *Main contact person:* Diego Ramiro
- *Contact email:* diego.ramiro@cchs.csic.es;
- *Technical contact person:* same
- *Technical contact email:* same

Short description of the use case: field, discipline, community

European governments are moving towards new statistical systems, abandoning costly statistical operations and making greater use of the de-identified administrative data routinely collected by government departments and other agencies. Such data, made accessible for research in ways that prevent the identification of individuals, will provide a robust evidence base to inform research and policy development, implementation and evaluation, while at the same time allowing an in-depth understanding of the rapid sociodemographic changes that are underlying the transformation of European societies. Socio-demographic and health microdata have an important value to researchers from a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines. The access to this information requires the signature of agreements, clearance of users and the use of physical secured rooms. SIESTA will provide a set of tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access and the implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center. This will reduce the burden that statistical offices have on preparing tailored data for individual requests which takes their time from other statistical production, and will allow a wider re-use of statistical and administrative data.

The user’s community will be those interested in Geo-spatial statistical production and analysis, demographers, economists, geographers, health professionals, governmental and statistical agencies, policy makers and finally the general public via the generation of new statistical and administrative products.

II. Use case description

1. Presentation

An introductory section describing the use case in general terms (objectives, means, partners, etc.)

The aim of this WP is to provide a set of tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyze in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access. The implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center that can reduce the current situation faced by statistical producers with greater demands by society for information on new issues (such as globalization, welfare indicators beyond

GDP, cohabitation, longevity, etc.), greater speed and granularity in the dissemination of data and an increase in quality assurance. This will provide a robust evidence base to inform research and policy development, implementation and evaluation, while at the same time allowing an in-depth understanding of the rapid sociodemographic changes that are underlying the transformation of European societies. Socio-demographic and health microdata have an important value to researchers from a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines.

This main aim will be achieved via:

- the development of tools to cross datasets with individual identification in an automatic way and to provide statistical outputs without privacy concerns.
- the development of tools able to cross-check data sets with constraints even in the case in which the identification is not direct, but only common characteristics.
- by the implementation of a pilot Intermediate Data Center.
- by building synthetic populations compliant with the statistics of the real ones from the microdata of generic surveys.

The Lead Partner is CSIC (IEGD-IFISC), Participants: INE, JdIC.

2. Expectations within the SIESTA project

The expectations within the SIESTA project involves the building and understanding of methods for linking different datasets preserving the confidentiality of the different datasets involved. The implementation of these methods and tools with real data. The creation of methods and tools to build synthetic datasets compliant with the statistics of the real ones from the microdata of generic surveys which can be later on re-used for statistical analysis. And finally to test the legal and operational possibility of setting up an intermediate data center.

What do you think could be your main objectives to be achieved within the SIESTA project in relation to this Use Case?

- Develop and/or test methods and tools to link sensitive datasets with identified microdata preserving confidentiality. Different scenarios would be considered including one in which different datasets are in different premises of different data owners.
- Analyze how confidentiality is preserved in the linking process and in the output of this process.
- Develop and/or test methods and tools to link sensitive datasets with incomplete identification.
- Cross check the results of these methods.
- Study the viability of setting up intermediate services between data providers and data users for scientific purposes preserving data confidentiality
- Develop and/or test methods and tools to generate synthetic data that reproduce the goal variables of a project without the privacy concerns of working with sensitive microdata

What do you think you will be able to do after the project that you could not now?

- Ease the access to sensitive data to researchers for scientific purposes.

- Access to sensitive data and link different datasets located in different premises while preserving the confidentiality of the data along the process and the output
- Generate synthetic data with more effectiveness and less cost for sensitive microdata.
- Link sensitive datasets, with complete or incomplete identification of microdata, in an array of attributes chosen by the user.

Please try to identify what are the requirements that could make a difference on this Use Case at technical level and that are not solved by now.

- Same requirements that those we have mentioned in the first question on this set of questions.

III. Technical description

1. Community management

Which tools are you using for authentication/authorization?

It depends on the privacy concerns of the data. We have 3 levels of risks and availability of the data:

1. Data with low risk: normally statistical Institutes provide these data available as public users files. They are available in their own web site (for example www.ine.es)
2. Data with medium risk: defined such risk as there exists a possible/probable indirect identification. Only researchers for scientific projects can access the data. Normally the data is sent to the researchers on the premise of justified scientific research after a process of accreditation of the research and the entity that researcher belongs to.
3. Data with high risk: data highly sensitive and direct identification very probable. Access only available within secure premises located in the statistical offices after this accreditation process.

Do you have a specific procedure for accepting new members into your community?

Yes, normally Statistical Offices and Governmental Data producers have a complete protocol to access the data. First of all, the entity must be recognised as a public institution.

To verify this information, they must meet these conditions:

1. Show they are recognised as public researcher in statistics,
2. Show what is the main purpose/activity of the entity,
3. Comply with some characteristics regarding organization and resources (for analysis, security, etc...)

These conditions are evaluated by an internal committee within the Statistical Offices. This is the case of INE.

After being recognised as a public institution, if a researcher of this entity wants to make a proposal for accessing to data they have to follow these steps:

1. Make a proposal with a description of the project which must include viability, need to access confidential microdata, access form of the data, security measures, researchers involved and dissemination of results. The project must follow all the legal requirements.
2. A committee approves or rejects the proposal with a motivated report.

If you are using different tools, how are they interacting with each other?

If the research is conducted in one of the secure settings, it is provided the more common tools for doing statistical analysis. Otherwise, the tools used are the ones that the research groups find more suitable for their projects.

2. Analysis pipelines

Describe the flow of data from local resources (i.e. user laptop) to the infrastructure, from one infrastructure to another.

We think it is described in the previous set of questions.

Do you need a multi-site federation?

We do not need, but it is a possibility that could be worth investigating as it can reduce the paperwork and personnel involved for granting access and facilitate/ease the access to researchers

Do you regularly need to transfer data among distributed datacenters?

We attend data requirements for scientific purposes (according with the procedure previously explained) almost constantly. Some of them, as we have indicated, are sent to the premises of the researcher.

Is there a workflow controlled by experts in the community that regulates the needed data management or every user can make DM requests?

The data are served to researchers (in their premises or in the secure data centers).

3. Data staging and compute platform

This section details the tasks that will need to be carried out on the SIESTA secure platform, as well as the requirements of the use case in relation to this platform. For example, do you need a graphical / interactive interface to the compute platform or specific hardware resources like NPU, GPU, FPGA accelerators.

Not from our side (INE)

What applications are you planning to use?

None from our side (INE)

Which operating systems do you need on the secure platform (Linux, Windows).

No preferences (INE)

Do you need a container runtime (e.g. docker). These requirements are not only technical, but also organizational and legal (for example, the software should only be accessed by a specific user / group).

Not from our side (INE)

4. Trusted computing

In your case, can you describe what you expect from a trusted computing platform?

Full compliance of legal restrictions for use and transmission of sensitive microdata.

We have explained this previously. Give us and provide to other access to sensitive microdata assuring the full compliance with legal restrictions.

What services are you looking for that are not yet available?

All those we have mentioned previously: methods to link datasets preserving confidentiality and for generating synthetic data.

What services are you already using that you would like to keep using on the secure platform?

Any update in the service is welcome but, security measures cannot be lowered as it was stated previously. Normally Statistical Offices are not using any kind of services but the procedure we have explained. As producer of National Statistics the Offices take security and confidentiality of the data very seriously.

IV. Data description

In this section, each kind of data (input, output) that will be processed or stored on the SIESTA infrastructure should be described. If you have a Data Management Plan (DMP) you can reuse parts of it to provide answers. Specific elements for input or output data are also listed in the dedicated sections.

The following items should be covered for each kind of data:

CENSO DE POBLACIÓN Y VIVIENDAS 2021 (VIVIENDAS). Public user file

NOTE: It is possible that this data set changes along the develop of the project. If more identification variables should be added, more data sensitivity would be involved and some of the detailed information we provided below must be changed.

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
DSL 1
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
Publicly available
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*
136 MB
- *Legal constraints (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)*
Ley de la Función Estadística Pública

Reglamento General de Protección de Datos

This specific dataset could be shared (it is freely available in our web)

No ethical or legal issues with this specific dataset (it is freely available in our web)

- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted?*
No for this specific dataset
- *Is an encryption management service needed? .*
No for this specific dataset
- *Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
No for this specific dataset
- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others (DMP: 3.2.2.2)*
Answered in previous questions.
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
No

CENSO DE POBLACIÓN Y VIVIENDAS 2021 (Personas y hogares). Public user file

NOTE: It is possible that this data set changes along the develop of the project. If more identification variables should be added, more data sensitivity would be involved and some of the detailed information we provided below must be changed.

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
DSL 1
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
Publicly available
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*
1,2 GB
- *Legal constraints (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)*
Ley de la Función Estadística Pública
Reglamento General de Protección de Datos
This specific dataset could be shared (it is freely available in our web)
No ethical or legal issues with this specific dataset (it is freely available in our web)
- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted?*
No for this specific dataset
- *Is an encryption management service needed? .*
No for this specific dataset
- *Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
No for this specific dataset

- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others (DMP: 3.2.2.2)*
Answered in previous questions.
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
No

ENCUESTA DE CONDICIONES DE VIDA (Fichero transversal). Public user file

NOTE: It is possible that this data set changes along the develop of the project. If more identification variables should be added, more data sensitivity would be involved and some of the detailed information we provided below must be changed.

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
DSL 1
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
Publicly available
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*
55,5 MB
- *Legal constraints (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)*
Ley de la Función Estadística Pública
Reglamento General de Protección de Datos
This specific dataset could be shared (it is freely available in our web)
No ethical or legal issues with this specific dataset (it is freely available in our web)
- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted?*
No for this specific dataset
- *Is an encryption management service needed? .*
No for this specific dataset
- *Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
No for this specific dataset
- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others (DMP: 3.2.2.2)*
Answered in previous questions.
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
No

ENCUESTA NACIONAL DE SALUD (Public user file)

NOTE: It is possible that this data set changes along the develop of the project. If more identification variables should be added, more data sensitivity would be involved and some of the detailed information we provided in the rest of the questionnaire must be changed.

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
DSL 1
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
Publicly available
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*
55,5 MB
- *Legal constraints (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)*
Ley de la Función Estadística Pública
Reglamento General de Protección de Datos
This specific dataset could be shared (it is freely available in our web)
No ethical or legal issues with this specific dataset (it is freely available in our web)
- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted?*
No for this specific dataset
- *Is an encryption management service needed? .*
No for this specific dataset
- *Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
No for this specific dataset
- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others (DMP: 3.2.2.2)*
Answered in previous questions.
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
No

DATOS DE RENTA

- *Data and metadata sensitivity (see the data sensitivity levels table at the end of the questionnaire), as well as the ethical aspects (DMP: Section 6)*
DSL 6
- *Data access (DMP: Section 3.2)*
Very limited access. Only for previously authorized staff according to the rules of the Tax Authority
- *Data size (DMP: Q 1.1.6)*

Unknown in this initial stage of the project, but no bigger than the censuses datasets

- *Legal constraints* (DMP: Q 3.2.2.2 & Q 6.1.1)
Ley de la Función Estadística Pública
Reglamento General de Protección de Datos
Ley General Tributaria
- *In particular, the following questions should be addressed: Does the data need to be encrypted?*
Identified data could not be exported from Tax Agency servers. Anonymised data could be extracted from Tax Agency servers only with its previous acceptance.
- *Is an encryption management service needed?* .
No for this specific dataset
- *Should a key store service be provided by the infrastructure?*
Yes
- *How long the key management service should guarantee encryption security?*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Should data access be restricted? i.e. open to some groups, restricted to others* (DMP: 3.2.2.2)
Answered in previous questions.
- *The granularity of access control: permissions are set to single users or user groups (communities). Specify through examples if there are roles with special access rights to the data.*
Answered in previous questions.
- *Do you need a service for auditing data accesses?*
Yes

1. Input Data

Data sources

- *What is the origin or the provenance of the dataset?* (DMP: 1.1.8)
Data come from official surveys and/or from administrative registers. In any case, they are not the raw data but data after being processed by a statistics production process.
- *What are the types of the collected data (images, numbers, text, ...)?* (DMP: 1.1.4 & 1.1.5)
Numbers. Different numeric formats.
- *Which data formats are used? Is there any specification/standard?*
Usual numeric formats are used.
- *Is there any metadata associated with the data?*
Yes
- *Where is the data (if any) currently stored (type of storage)?*
In the INE (National Statistics Institute of Spain) servers and in the Spanish Tax Agency
- *What is the expected size (GiB, TB)?* (DMP: 1.1.6)
Answered for each data sets in previous questions.
- *How frequently is data updated?*

Data about population censuses and living conditions are published each year. Data from the National Health Survey are published every five years. Data from Tax Agency are published annually.

- *At which rate is the data collected (e.g. 100GiB/year)?*
All the data are completely renewed with the same frequency that it is mentioned in the previous question.
- *How much storage may be required for the duration of the project?*
- *How and when (if data access scheduling is required) can the data be accessed? (DMP: few questions in section 3.2)*
As all of the data coming from INE are public use files all of them can be publicly accessed. They are released as soon as the results of the statistics are published. INE publishes an official released calendar in the web: <https://www.ine.es/dynt3/Calendario/calenHTML.htm>.

Data coming from Spanish Tax Agency can only be accessed with previous authorisation from its owner.

- *Are there established de-identification/anonymisation methods for these data formats? Are they recognised standards/community best practices? Have you applied any of them beforehand?*
Yes, there is a process for the anonymization of the data following current practices within the statistical community. This process is run prior to the moment where the data are released.

Data uses

- *What types of analysis are you planning to perform on these data (statistical, image processing, etc.)?*

Most of the analysis which is performed with data from the National Statistical Offices

- *What type of software do you use for analyzing your data?*

This depends very much on the data users and their research Teams. For the analysis in Secure Settings common statistical software is used.

- *Will you use AI methods?*
 - *If yes: Do you want to run it in the cloud?*
 - *Should the inference run on a single computer?*
 - *How much memory does the training require?*
- *Do you need hardware accelerators? (e.g. GPU, FPGA, NPU)*
- *Are there any constraints for those accelerators:*
 - *Quantity (for the whole platform, per VM, etc.)*
 - *Memory (is there a minimum required)*
 - *type/brand/model/API requirements*
- *What deep learning framework is used (Tensorflow, PyTorch, etc), if any?*
- *What tools are used during experimentation (e.g. JupyterLab, PyCharm, VScode)?*

Privacy / confidentiality

- *Does the described dataset / output contain personal data? (DMP: 6.1.3)*
Yes, all of them.

- *Are you going to use confidential proprietary data, or have other access restrictions you would like to enforce?*
Tax Agency data have strong restrictions to be accessed.
- *Is this going to be actual or simulated data? If the latter, how was the data created?*
In the case of actual data is provided by the Statistical Offices. The production of simulated data, in the form of synthetic data will be one of the main objectives of this project.
- *Are you using previously anonymised data? How and by whom was the data anonymised?*
In some cases, yes. By the National Statistical Offices.
- *Can data be transferred to a third-party cloud? Can the data be transferred across borders inside the EEA?*
Yes
- *Is there associated metadata that raises any privacy concerns?*
No
- *Do you need to augment data for training purposes?*
- *Any other information governance restrictions from the data controller or authorities that should be taken into account?*
Those already mentioned regarding National Statistical Laws, and European and National Data privacy regulation.

2. Output Data

Data Sharing

The overall objective is to enhance the EOSC Exchange services by delivering a set of cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC, demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them. In this context it has to be explained how the data can be shared:

- *Are you planning to share your data with other researchers after the analysis?*
It is intended within the project to develop tools and methods to be able to exchange and disseminate data complying with all the security and respecting all the requirements on data privacy.
- *Are you planning to share aggregated statistics concerning your data? Do you need to apply additional privacy techniques before sharing these statistics (e.g. differential privacy)?*
Answered already in the questionnaire. But aggregated statistics are already produced, once anonymized and always complying with data privacy legislation.
- *Would you like to publicly release the analyzed/transformed resulting data?*
It will be one of the goals of this project to be able to publicly release data always complying with data privacy and ethical legislation.
- *What are your requirements regarding the privacy-usefulness trade-off?*
The Statistical Offices require very high standards on data privacy, therefore data will be released only if it complies with data privacy and ethical legislation.
- *Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?*

Already described in the document with the different Laws that all the National Statistical Offices need to follow.

ANNEX II - PERSONAS, EPICs, USER STORIES

Use case 1 (WP14) “Platform for epidemic data-driven modeling”

Personas

Daniela: Researcher in computational epidemiology

Alice: Policy-maker in public health

Diana: System administrator & data owner

Anna: Platform administrator (user management)

Daniela

Daniela works as a researcher in computational epidemiology, she needs to compare standard model results across countries on the forecast of an emerging disease spreading.

Thinks	<i>Daniela thinks that building the model framework is costly in terms of time and expertise in computation. Having similar results comparable across countries is a major “must” for her research. She thinks that she should be able to define the epidemic models needed to simulate the spreading of different diseases, should they be airborne human-to-human or vector borne as mosquito borne diseases.</i>
Sees	<i>Daniela sees that right now there is only a limited platform available for simulations based mainly on a population level (metapopulation) approach.</i>
Feels	<i>Feels that having a platform with an agent-based scale, in which the user had freedom to implement several containment measures and compare scenarios could be a large step forward for her research.</i>
Does	<i>Her intention is to publish these results in scientific journals and in collaboration with other groups to explain the disease basic propagation rules and inform public health interventions. She needs to download the simulation results for analysis locally and for the development of new metrics. She collaborates with colleagues at international level.</i>

Alice

Alice is a stakeholder in public health policy. She takes decisions at a technical level and must present scenarios of containment measures to the political level decision makers who are not experts in the field.

Thinks	That the decisions to be taken on containment measures to delay or minimize the epidemic propagation of an emerging disease must be based on quantitative analysis and on a data-driven approach. This requires building population or individual level models, such as agent-based models, that her institution does not have the expertise to develop.
Sees	Right now, these tools have been generated at population scale and are thought for global scale importation risk analyses. There is a need for more detailed models at the local level, in which potential interventions are more specific and potentially tailored to specific demographic groups.
Feels	That the containment scenario comparison is fundamental before taking decisions that can affect thousands of citizens and generate inequalities in the burden of disease and on mental health. She does not need to worry about the building of the models, or on the reliability of the data needed to inform them. A simple and flexible tool, allowing to describe disease transmission at individual level and with an attractive visual output would be fundamental.
Does	She briefs her decision council (Ministry or Government) with a portfolio of policies to delay or contain disease propagation. These are based on the results of the Siesta platforms and were obtained in a timely fashion, without need to rely on real time data streams from companies nor professional training of new personnel.

Diana

Diana is one of the system managers in charge of the modeling system of SIESTA. She has developed the epidemic models and collected the data needed for them.

Thinks	<i>Diana thinks that data must be safe, in some cases they are sensitive in terms of privacy and confidentiality and/or they are proprietary of third-parties that may require not to share them or to pass through their own platforms for sharing. However, at the same time the results of data-driven models are fundamental for informed decision making in social systems and in particular in public health.</i>
Sees	<i>A system to monitor the use of the platform and KPIs in terms of the user's activity in its interior.</i>

Feels	<i>She feels responsible for the performance of the system and especially knowing the high impact of the potential results, both in the scientific arena and in the policy making side. She knows that this system can be essential in an emergency situation as the one created by COVID-19, but also in smaller scale outbreaks.</i>
Does	<i>Diana configures and maintains all the systems on the infrastructures and monitors every service. She answers user tickets and responds to incidents. She updates the data behind the models as new releases are available from the official data sources. The whole system is prepared for this to represent a minimal work load, but it must be done with care.</i>

Anna

Diana is one of the SIESTA Platform managers.

Thinks	<i>Anna strives searches to give the best possible service to the platform users and she must consider their different level of access to the tools and datasets.</i>
Sees	<i>A system to monitor the use of the platform and KPIs in terms of the user's activity in its interior.</i>
Feels	<i>She feels responsible for keeping an ordered access to the tools developed in SIESTA and for its reliability in terms of computation capacity and resources needed in terms of ram memory or disk space.</i>
Does	<i>Anna configures and maintains the whole platform. She answers user tickets and responds to incidents.</i>

Problem Scenario + Alternatives Pairs + Value proposition

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
<p><i>Daniela works as a researcher in computational epidemiology, she needs to run epidemic models to explain the transmission of a new disease circulating in Europe and propose potential measures of intervention to the national public health agency.</i></p>	<p><i>She uses available web-platforms that only assess disease importation risk at country level and incidence in sub-national regions in the general population, without any insights on age, gender, occupation of the infected population. She cannot inform targeted interventions on specific settings, like school or workplaces, nor tailor policies on demographic groups.</i></p>	<p><i>SIESTA will offer a secure environment where state-of-the-art epidemic models will be usable by experts, like researchers or public health agents, to produce analytics on ongoing or past outbreaks at multiple scales, ranging from agent-based models, to age-structured models and meta-population models.</i></p>
<p><i>Bob teaches Epidemiology at the University and wants to show the students what is the functionality of current epidemic models like "Polymod" age-structured models. He does not have time to build a new epidemic model from scratch and is looking for a simple online platform that can reproduce some basic phenomena of epidemic spreading.</i></p>	<p><i>He builds the model from scratch, taking several hours of his time, or relies on published code from the literature. Data is often missing or not shared by previous modelers and results visualization is another task that will take more of his time for this lecture.</i></p>	<p><i>SIESTA will offer a secure environment where state-of-the-art epidemic models will be usable by the general public to increase the understanding of epidemic modeling from the general population and foster trust in health institutions from the public. A user-friendly interface will provide basic and intuitive visualization tools to showcase the outcomes of the platform models.</i></p>

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
<p><i>Mason wants to assess the risk of local outbreaks of Dengue developing in Italy due to increased disease incidence in South America and the prevalence of vectors in his country.</i></p> <p><i>The results of these analyses may raise the alert in local public health agencies and promptly trigger prevention measures in the population.</i></p>	<p><i>He is developing a model following codes shared by previous literature, but data on vector species is missing and mobility data encoding trips from South America to Europe are outdated. He runs the model on outdated mobility data and homogeneous distributions of vectors. His research will be less informative than he aspired to.</i></p>	<p><i>In the SIESTA platform, regional level data on prevalence of disease vectors, such as Aedes Albopictus mosquitoes, will be available and usable to inform vector borne diseases models to assess the risk of local transmission in the population.</i></p>
<p><i>Diana needs to control which users are accessing some particular datasets.</i></p>	<p><i>She checks the logs to check specific requests to data.</i></p>	<p><i>SIESTA will offer a user management and data control system to trigger any access to data taking into account different levels of security.</i></p>
<p><i>Alice needs to prepare a report for the Minister on the propagation of a new emerging disease.</i></p>	<p><i>Current alternatives imply either very simplified theoretical models or models as Glean not adapted to city scale since they are global.</i></p>	<p><i>SIESTA will offer a tool based on updated population, mobility and demographic data able to explore containment measures at individual and local scales.</i></p>

EPICs and User stories

UC1.E01 “Setup own research environment inside the platform”

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

- (c)** - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first
- (m)** - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project
- (o)** - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC1.E01.US01</p> <p>As a researcher I want to be able to set up my own research environment inside the platform i.e., install libraries and dependencies needed for running the analysis methods.</p>	<p>Ensure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User has access to verified repositories for the different kind of software they want to install (e.g., pypi, networkx, statsmodels) • Is possible to add another verified artifacts/software source if needed. • The system checks the software about to be run for known vulnerabilities
<p>UC1.E01.US02</p> <p>As a researcher I want to be able to access a user interface and build my own epidemic model and exploiting the available data (agent based, age-structured, meta-pop, vector borne disease model)</p>	<p>Ensure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User has access to a user interface, e.g. Jupyter notebook or R, designed for experts, to build their custom model using Python, R or C++ • User interface can access the available datasets (to choose among the synthetic population, the mixing matrices, the meta-pop OD matrices and the vectors prevalences)
<p>UC1.E01.US03</p> <p>As a system admin, I want to configure the list of available libraries to limit the actions to be done by the user over data</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries are up to date and no security issues are active • Users can check if a specific library is eligible
<p>UC1.E01.US04</p> <p>As a system admin, I want to manage the computing resources quota of users to equalize the availability.</p>	<p>Make sure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users do not wait too much to get resources • Low memory jobs are prioritized • A memory threshold is imposed to jobs in order to avoid memory saturation and machine crash

UC1.E02 “Data accessing and reuse”

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

(c) - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first

(m) - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project

(o) - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC1.E01.US01 As an epidemic modeler I want to upload any extra data I may need for my analysis, be it public or private, in order to complement the models.</p>	<p>Ensure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage environment includes tools to ensure the security and the proper treatment of sensitive private data uploaded by the user • The level of anonymity can be checked, and further anonymization techniques can be applied in a seamless way, if needed • Is possible to add other sort of data, public or private, maintaining confidentiality (e.g. vaccination data provided under NDA by a public health agency)
<p>UC1.E01.US02 As an epidemic modeler I want to re-use the outputs of previous jobs in order to make statistical analyses of stochastic models results.</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous jobs results are stored in a private environment accessible by the user only • The user is informed that storage space is limited to a certain amount and receives reminders to download the outputs from time to time • Outputs older than a certain period are deleted automatically • Users may be organized in groups
<p>UC1.E01.US03 As a researcher, I want to get a list of datasets to select which will be included in my processing</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The permissions are well explained • The actions that can be done on specific data are described
<p>UC1.E01.US04 As a researcher, I want to see the metadata of all existing data to request access to specific datasets</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only some metadata is shared taking into account ethics, laws, etc. • The request should be well justified.

Use case 2 (WP15) “Medical (Neuro)Imaging”

Personas

Persona A - Anne is the data owner of a medical dataset

Persona B - Rob is a PhD student who wants to (re)analyze Anne’s data.

Persona A

Anne works in a research institute. She is a scientist by training and handles a lot of data.

Thinks	<i>Anne thinks that providing well-curated data allows other people to ask additional questions and possibly combine results from multiple studies, thus increasing the outputs from research projects.</i>
Sees	<i>Anne sees how difficult it is to share personal data under GDPR. She sees how easy it is in, for example, the USA and wishes it could be the same for her.</i>
Feels	<i>When other researchers ask for the datasets, she feels anxious because she knows that negotiating research agreements with layers takes a long time and a lot of effort.</i>
Does	<i>Anne has been curating data using international standards for many years now (for WP15 it means using BIDS https://bids.neuroimaging.io/).</i>

Persona B

Rob is a PhD student (medical, biomedical, biology -- not software dev) who wants to access data in order to test a hypothesis before starting to collect new data.

Thinks	<i>Rob thinks it should be easy and quick to access existing datasets. This is important because he has only 3 years to do his PhD.</i>
Sees	<i>He sees that recent publications reuse data to test hypotheses on existing data and/or use them for power analyses.</i>
Feels	<i>When he reads about reusing data, he feels a bit jealous because it is very hard for him to do so with medical data.</i>
Does	<i>Rob is new to research and very enthusiastic to try out new solutions.</i>

Problem Scenario + Alternatives Pairs + Value proposition

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
<p>Rob needs to access Anne's data to carry out a new analysis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The data needs to be well organised/curated. - Rob needs some disk space and dedicated software to do the analysis. 	<p>Rob will ask his PhD supervisor if she can ask Anne for the data. A data transfer agreement (DTA) needs to be signed between institutions. Data will then be sent between institutions. This will likely happen but not in a useful time frame for Rob. The analysis will take place at the institution on their PCs/server.</p>	<p>Having a place where Anne can deposit data to be processed by Rob. With SIESTA, because Rob will only see anonymised data, there is no need for DTA, to shorten the time between request and access, solving Rob's problem and allowing better research.</p>

EPICs and User stories

“As a data owner, I want to deposit data in safe environment without having to sign paperwork every time, so that I can share data as required by funders and increase research outputs”

- 1 - my institution sign paperwork for where to deposit data
- 2 - prepare/curate datasets using recommended standards
- 3 - deposit datasets
- 4 - dataset is checked by the platform (BIDS validator) → some parts need redone

“As a researcher, I want to be able to access data without having to sign paperwork that delay my projects, so that I can quickly test new ideas to generate new research outputs”

- 1 - sign in to a platform (some regulatory text about not trying to identify, or export personal information)
- 2 - import/ask for dedicated software applications
- 3 - test my scripts (on anonymous data provided by SIESTA)
- 4 - execute my scripts (on real personal data) -- recorded actions for audits
- 5 - examine results and possibly iterate steps 3-4 if needed
- 6 - export some results/ aggregated data (tables csv, figures) - those are anonymous

Use case 4 (WP17) “Text Anonymization on Sensitive Data”

Personas

Antonio: Cybersecurity reports manager

Enrique: ML scientist who wants to train an NLP model to classify reports

David: Technical administrator (user management)

Antonio

Antonio is working in a Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) as a cybersecurity technician. He is the manager of the incident reports in a CERT.

<p>Thinks</p>	<p><i>[Persona] thinks [things should be different in a certain way]. This is important because [why?]</i> <i>Antonio thinks that there is a need to classify CERT or crime reports into categories in an automatic way. These reports are written as unstructured text. However, the data needed to train the classification models often contain sensitive or private data (e.g. names, locations, IPs, etc.), so such data cannot be disclosed by the interested authorities. Therefore, the models cannot be trained and, consequently, the automatic classification of such reports is not possible. Antonio thinks that it would be very useful to have a tool that anonymizes reports containing sensitive data, with a focus on the subsequent text classification. The tool should provide tracking of the usage of the data. This tool is important because the anonymized text would make it possible to share it with people outside CERT to create the classification models to automate this task.</i></p>
<p>Sees</p>	<p><i>[In certain situation], [persona] sees [key observation of importance]. [Repeat, etc]</i> <i>Reports of data breaches in the scientific community increase the need for awareness of potential vulnerabilities as well as keeping up to date with changes in data protection regulations. Antonio sees new emerging technologies and platforms promising enhanced security and analytical capabilities, specially in the cloud. Collaboration and data sharing is beneficial for research</i></p>
<p>Feels</p>	<p><i>When [some event], persona feels [emotion]. It's [cause] that makes them feel this way.</i> <i>Antonio feels a sense of responsibility for keeping safe CERT reports, knowing that any breach could harm victims of the reports and adversely interfere in legal proceedings. However, despite the challenges, Antonio feels hopeful and optimistic about the potential of new technologies based on artificial intelligence and secure cloud environments to help in the automatic classification of text reports with anonymized sensitive data.</i></p>
<p>Does</p>	<p><i>[Persona] [does activity] [x] times per [period].</i> <i>When researchers request access to use CERT reports, Antonio sometimes has to deny it due to the sensitiveness of the data. When he has permission to share the sensitive data, he works closely with the institution's IT and legal teams to ensure compliance with data protection regulations and to address any potential vulnerabilities. Antonio needs to manually annotate and prioritize the cyber-indictment reports he receives on a regular basis.</i></p>

Enrique

Enrique is an artificial intelligence researcher who works on applying and creating machine and deep learning models for natural language processing. One of his lines of research focuses on the classification of cyber incidents reports to help in the understanding of the reports.

Thinks	<p><i>[Persona] thinks [things should be different in a certain way]. This is important because [why?]</i> <i>Enrique thinks that he could improve the performance and the results of his AI-based models if he had more data at his disposal for training, coming from different and more diverse centers.</i></p>
Sees	<p><i>[In certain situation], [persona] sees [key observation of importance]. [Repeat, etc]</i> <i>Enrique is aware of techniques that can be useful to get more out of his research on cyber incidents classification, but he does not have enough reports to train and test his models. He sees that he needs to work with real reports but it is not possible because they contain sensitive data such as names, addresses,... He also sees that collaboration in this field is essential in order to create more robust models. However, he sees that when working with such sensitive data it is difficult to enhance collaboration and that additional privacy techniques need to be applied.</i></p>
Feels	<p><i>When [some event], persona feels [emotion]. It's [cause] that makes them feel this way.</i> <i>Enrique feels that it is important for his research to work within trusted research environments, ensuring the integrity and security of the data he uses as input to his models. In addition, he feels it is imperative that the privacy of the data he uses is protected prior to his access to the data.</i></p>
Does	<p><i>[Persona] [does activity] [x] times per [period].</i> <i>Enrique is already developing AI models for allowing classification of unstructured text. He is currently working with publicly shared texts that come from non sensitive cyber reports or with simulated data. However, he wants to expand his research to real sensitive reports. Moreover, he needs to access computational resources, and this must be done securely. He works on high performance computing centers using resources such as GPUs.</i></p>

David

David is a technical systems administrator expert in computer science. He works in a research group and is responsible for the team's infrastructure.

Thinks	<i>David thinks that it is important that the systems are updated, robust and scalable. David thinks that sensitive data should be managed properly and any action over that should be registered.</i>
Sees	<i>A system to monitor the environments for use case 4. David sees logs to understand problems and technical documentation to maintain the environments.</i>
Feels	<i>David feels responsible for the continuous behavior of the systems and the maintenance of the environments.</i>
Does	<i>David manages the infrastructures and computing resources and monitors every service for use case 4. He answers user tickets and responds to incidents.</i>

Problem Scenario + Alternatives Pairs + Value proposition

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
<i>[What problems, needs does persona have in the area?]</i>	<i>[What do they do right now to solve this problem/meet this need?]</i>	<i>[What product ideas do the problem scenarios and current alternatives give you?] [What component of the AI platform may solve the problem?]</i>
Antonio needs to classify cyberincident reports which contain sensitive data such as names, addresses, etc. depending on the type of the cyberincident..	He classifies the cyberincident reports manually, either himself or authorized members of his team.	SIESTA will offer a secure environment where to upload the cyberincident reports and anonymize them. The anonymized reports can be used by AI scientists to train classification models so new cyberincident reports can be automatically classified by such models.
Enrique wants to train innovative NLP-based models to classify cyberincident reports.	He is using synthetic cyberincident reports in the shape of unstructured texts that try to simulate real reports.	SIESTA will provide a safe environment where researchers can connect remotely and train classification models on real reports that have previously been anonymized or pseudoanonymized
David needs to control which users are accessing some particular models and manage the computing resources quota of users.	He checks the logs to check specific requests to models and resources.	SIESTA will offer a user management and data control system to trigger any access to models and allocate resources for researchers that want to access the SIESTA platform.

EPICs and User stories

UC4.E01 “Setup own research environment inside the platform”

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

- (c)** - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first
- (m)** - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project
- (o)** - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
UC4.E01.US01 As a researcher, I want to be able to set up a research environment inside the platform, i.e., install libraries and dependencies needed for running the researchers’ models.	Ensure that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (c) Users can set up environments and have access to verified repositories for the different kinds of software they want to install (e.g., pypi).
UC4.E01.US02 As a system admin, I want to manage the computing resources quota of users to prioritize the availability.	Make sure that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (o) Users do not wait too long to get resources.
UC4.E01.US03 As a system admin, I want to configure the list of available classification models to limit the actions to be done by the user over data	Make sure that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (m) Available models are at a final version and no security issues are active • (o) Users can check if a specific model is eligible

UC4.E02 “Data accessing and use”

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

(c) - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first

(m) - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project

(o) - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC4.E02.US01</p> <p>As a CERT team member, I want to upload incident reports to the platform and create anonymized versions that can be shared to train classification models.</p>	<p>Ensure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (c) CERT team members have access to upload incidents to a repository in the platform. • (c) The anonymization tools are working properly. • (c) Only the anonymized documents will be available for researchers, who can either (i) download them or (ii) use them to train the classification models within the platform.
<p>UC4.E02.US02</p> <p>As a CERT team member, I want to control who can access or download which anonymized cyberincident reports</p>	<p>Ensure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (m) CERT team members can grant permissions to users for accessing the anonymized reports in the platform. • (m) CERT team members can grant permissions to users for downloading the anonymized reports in the platform.
<p>UC4.E02.US03</p> <p>As a researcher, I want to upload my classification models to the platform, and train models on the anonymized data.</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (c) Users can upload classification models to the platform. • (m) Users can generate or modify code in the platform. • (c) Users can only access anonymized data. • (c) The system checks the software about to be run for known vulnerabilities.
<p>UC4.E02.US04</p> <p>As a CERT team member, I want to download a researcher’s model or try it on new incident reports. If the classification of the new incident report is incorrect I want to send an issue to the researcher/developer of the classification model.</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (c) CERT team members can access, run, or download the classification models created and trained by researchers. • (m) CERT team members can raise issues.
<p>UC4.E02.US05</p> <p>As a CERT team member I want to check if the reports have been properly anonymized and, if that is not the case, I want to do it manually or raise an issue to the</p>	<p>Make sure that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (m) CERT team members can edit the text of the anonymized reports. • (o) CERT team members can raise issues about the anonymization to the SIESTA

User story	Test case
developers.	administrators
UC4.E02.US06 As a CERT team member, I want to track the use of the anonymized data.	Make sure that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (m) A log of the researchers that are accessing the data is maintained

Use case 5 (WP18) “Demography”

Personas

Persona A: **Academic Researcher**

Persona B: **Data Policy Officer**

Persona C: **Data Provider**

Persona A: Academic Researcher

A scientific researcher working with demographic and other sociodemographic or socioeconomic sources. They often require quick and easy access to multiple data sources, including linked anonymized population data.

Thinks	<i>The researcher thinks data access should be streamlined and user-friendly. This is important because it saves time and enhances the quality and efficiency of their research.</i>
Sees	<i>In a data repository, the researcher sees a need for a centralized platform or a way where multiple data sources are easily accessible and linked. When looking at current systems, they see fragmented and often incomplete datasets.</i>
Feels	<i>When encountering data access issues, the researcher feels frustrated. It's the inefficiency and complexity of navigating multiple systems that makes them feel this way.</i>
Does	<i>The researcher accesses demographic and socioeconomic or sociodemographic population data 3-4 times per week.</i>

Persona B: Data Policy Officer

A data policy officer interested in linking multiple administrative sources in an effective way to support data-driven decision-making and policy formulation within a Public Administration.

Thinks	<i>The data policy officer thinks data integration should be seamless and secure. This is important because it ensures comprehensive and reliable datasets for policy development. And would like to link as many different data sources as possible.</i>
Sees	<i>In inter-agency meetings, the officer sees a need for improved data linkage between departments. When reviewing current data policies, they see gaps and inefficiencies in data sharing protocols. Sometimes they see security concerns that inhibit data sharing or fragmented data of different quality between administrations.</i>

Feels	<i>When data from various sources do not align, the policy officer feels concerned. It's the potential for inaccurate policy outcomes that makes them feel this way.</i>
Does	<i>The policy officer coordinates data integration efforts and policy reviews 2-3 times per month.</i>

Persona C: Data Provider.

A data provider, such as an institute of statistics or another official agency, interested in providing users with linked anonymized rich data on population, sociodemographic or socioeconomic information, preserving data privacy and statistical anonymity .

Thinks	<i>The data provider thinks data should be comprehensive and anonymized for user safety and utility. This is important because it maintains user trust and compliance with privacy regulations. The data (statistics) needs to be diffused and reused by the public and private sector, always preserving data privacy and security.</i>
Sees	<i>In data management systems, the provider sees opportunities for enhancing data linkage and anonymization processes. When engaging with data users, they see a demand for richer, more detailed datasets. But they find it difficult to link their own data with others, often produced by other governmental agencies.</i>
Feels	<i>When users report difficulties in accessing or using data, the provider feels responsible. It's the commitment to service quality and user satisfaction that makes them feel this way. They feel it is rather difficult to link sensitive data from different agencies without compromising data privacy and security.</i>
Does	<i>The data provider updates and releases new datasets on a regular basis (depending on the dataset) and normally established by public statistical laws which regulate quality and main characteristics.</i>

Problem Scenario + Alternatives Pairs + Value proposition

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
<p><i>[What problems, needs does persona have in the area?]</i></p>	<p><i>[What do they do right now to solve this problem/meet this need?]</i></p>	<p><i>[What product ideas do the problem scenarios and current alternatives give you?]</i> <i>[What component of the AI platform may solve the problem?]</i></p>
<p>Needs quick and easy access to multiple data sources for comprehensive sociodemographic and socioeconomic research.</p> <p>Requires linked anonymized population data to perform accurate analyses and draw meaningful conclusions.</p> <p>Struggles with fragmented and incomplete datasets that hinder research efficiency and quality.</p>	<p>Manually searching and compiling data from various sources, often leading to time-consuming and error-prone processes.</p> <p>Using multiple platforms and databases that lack integration, making data linkage and analysis cumbersome.</p>	<p>Value Proposition: Develop a centralized, secure environment that provides seamless access to multiple sociodemographic or socioeconomic data sources coming from different administrative bodies. Implement advanced data linkage capabilities within and across multiple datasets inter and across state agencies to ensure complete and accurate datasets. Offer user-friendly interfaces and tools for easy data access and analysis.</p> <p>Component of the AI Platform: A data integration or data linkage module that automates the linkage of multiple sociodemographic or socioeconomic datasets. An advanced analytics toolkit that enables researchers to perform complex statistical analyses with ease.</p>
<p>Needs to provide users with comprehensive, linked anonymized data on the population.</p> <p>Seeks to enhance data linkage and anonymization processes to maintain user trust and compliance with privacy regulations.</p> <p>Faces demand for richer, more detailed datasets from users.</p>	<p>Uses traditional data management and anonymization techniques.</p> <p>Releases datasets on a set schedule without much flexibility for user-specific needs.</p> <p>Receives feedback on data difficulties but may lack the resources for immediate improvement or service to users.</p>	<p>Value Proposition: Develop a secure platform that automates data linkage across databases and statistical agencies and anonymization processes to enhance efficiency and security. Offer advanced anonymization techniques to ensure user privacy while providing rich, detailed datasets. To provide synthetic data which can be used for research without compromising data privacy and security. Provide tools for easy data sharing and access for users.</p>

Problem Scenarios / Jobs-to-be-Done	Current Alternative	Value proposition
		<p>Component of the AI Platform: Cutting-edge statistical models and AI algorithms to improve the richness and anonymity of provided datasets. A user-friendly data access interface that allows easy and secure sharing of anonymized data with researchers and policy makers.</p>

EPICs and User stories

UC5.E01 Centralized Data Access and Integration for Researchers

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

- (c) - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first
- (m) - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project
- (o) - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC5.E01.US01</p> <p>As a scientific researcher, I want to access a centralized platform with integrated population socioeconomic or sociodemographic data, so that I can streamline my research process and improve data accuracy.</p>	<p>Verify that the platform integrates data from multiple sources and presents it in a unified interface.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure data from different sources is accurately linked. • Confirm that data retrieval is quick and user-friendly. • Test for completeness and accuracy of the integrated datasets.
<p>UC5.E01.US02</p> <p>As a scientific researcher, I want the platform to include advanced search capabilities, so that I can easily find and link specific datasets relevant to my research.</p>	<p>Check that the search functionality can filter datasets based on various parameters (e.g., demographic variables, time periods).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure search results are relevant and comprehensive. • Test the responsiveness and accuracy of the search feature.

User story	Test case
<p>UC5.E01.US03</p> <p>As a scientific researcher, I want the platform to provide tools for linking anonymized data, so that I can use comprehensive datasets while maintaining data privacy.</p>	<p>Ensure that the data linking tools correctly anonymize and link data without compromising integrity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify that anonymized data cannot be re-identified. • Test the linkage accuracy and consistency across datasets.

UC5.E02 Secure Data Sharing and Integration for Policy Officers

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

(c) - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first

(m) - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project

(o) - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC5.E02.US01</p> <p>As a data policy officer, I want to securely share data between departments through the platform, so that I can ensure seamless data integration and collaboration.</p>	<p>Confirm that data sharing protocols comply with security standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure data encryption during transmission. • Verify user access controls and permissions are correctly implemented.
<p>UC5.E02.US02</p> <p>As a data policy officer, I want to have automated data integration processes, so that I can reduce manual effort and minimize errors in data linking.</p>	<p>Test the automation workflows for data integration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify that the automation correctly links data from different sources. • Ensure that error rates in data integration are minimized.

User story	Test case
<p>UC5.E02.US03</p> <p>As a data policy officer, I want to audit and track data sharing activities, so that I can maintain accountability and data integrity.</p>	<p>Check the platform’s auditing and tracking functionalities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure all data sharing activities are logged accurately. • Verify that audit logs are secure and tamper-proof. • Test the ability to generate reports on data sharing activities.

UC5.E03 Advanced Data Anonymization and Synthetic Data Generation for Providers

User stories and test cases

For Test cases, please, try to prioritize them as:

(c) - “critical”, i.e. has to be implemented first

(m) - “moderate”, important to have but can be done at the later stage of the project

(o) - “optional”, nice-to-have / improves the functionality but at a lower priority than the other two.

User story	Test case
<p>UC5.E03.US01</p> <p>As a data provider, I want to use advanced anonymization techniques within the platform, so that I can provide safe and usable data to researchers and policymakers.</p>	<p>Validate the effectiveness of anonymization techniques.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure data cannot be re-identified. • Verify the balance between data utility and privacy.
<p>UCX.E03.US02</p> <p>As a data provider, I want to generate synthetic population data using statistical models, so that I can offer rich datasets without compromising privacy.</p>	<p>Test the accuracy and utility of generated synthetic data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure synthetic data closely mimics real data without revealing actual identities. • Verify that synthetic data is useful for various research and policy-making applications.

User story	Test case
<p>UCX.E03.US03</p> <p>As a data provider, I want to provide customizable anonymization and synthetic data options, so that I can meet the diverse needs of different users without compromising statistical quality and security standards.</p>	<p>Check the customization options for anonymization and synthetic data generation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify that users can adjust parameters to suit their needs. • Ensure the platform maintains data privacy and utility across different customization settings.
<p>UCX.E03.US04</p> <p>As a data provider, I want to have an Intermediate Administrative Data Center which can provide customizable data and attend data requests from the public (researches) and private sector without compromising statistical privacy and security.</p>	<p>Check the viability of this administrative data center.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify legal viability and usefulness. • Ensure the platform maintains data privacy and utility across different customization settings.

ANNEX III - DATA SENSITIVITY LEVELS

The different levels of data sensitivity are described in the following table. These levels will be used to assess the data from the use case. Data sets can contain different kinds of data with different sensitivity levels. If such a data set has to be considered as a whole, the part with the highest sensitivity level should be taken into account.

Data sensitivity levels	Description
DSL1	Fully open data, no need to use a trusted research environment.
DSL2	Very low risk. Pseudonymised data with very low linking risk. Unlikely to cause harm.
DSL3	Low risk. Strongly pseudonymised datasets with some indirect identifiers.
DSL4	Average risk. Pseudonymised personal data and confidential organizations information.
DSL5	High risk. Weak or no de-identification and very sensitive commercial data.
DSL6	Very high risk. Very sensitive personal data or highly confidential government or commercial data.

ANNEX IV - SUMMARY OF CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING PROJECTS

Project	Maturity	Development	Requirement	Licence	Installation	App adaptation	App deployment	App execution
Gramine	Production (ver. 1.7)	Active (~22 commits/month)	Intel SGX	LGPL 3.0	Easy (packages for major Linux distributions)	No source modification, just rebuilding	Container images via project tool	Gramine CLI
Islet	Production (ver. 1.0)	Active (~43 commits/month)	ARMv9 CCA	Apache 2.0	Medium (only source code in the release)	Optionally, SDK provided	Binary	Using Islet RMM (Realm Management Monitor)
Keystone	Production (ver. 1.0.0)	Low (~1 commit/moth)	RISC-V	BSD-3-Clause	Medium (only source code in the release)	Yes	Binary	Using Qemu, FireSim (FPGA) or SiFive HiFive Unleashed board
Veracruz	Stable version veracruz/base: v23.12 for Linux system	Last release (May 9th, 2024)	Docker installation	MIT	Easy (package repositories for Debian 22/11, Ubuntu 22.04/20.04, e.g: Kali 2021-2023)	Needs to be compiled in WebAssembly, SDK also provided	Containers	Not relevant
VERAISON	Mature, Linux system.	Still under improvement (updates were released on May 15th, 2024)	Docker install	Apache-2.0	Easy (make sure to meet the installation requirements)	Not applicable	Containers	Not relevant
VirTEE	V1.2 library SEV-SNP update	active since July 2023	3rd Gen or later AMD	Apache-2.0	Easy (make sure to meet the	Not applicable	Binaries	

Project	Maturity	Development	Requirement	Licence	Installation	App adaptation	App deployment	App execution
			EPYC processors		installation requirements)			
Occlum	beta version (0.30.1) for Linux	Active since Feb 2019	Intel SGX or Intel FLC	BSD License	pre built Occlum docker container	needs to be compiled by occlum-gcc	using occlum commands	using occlum commands
Open Enclave SDK	stable versions for Windows and Linux	Active since Aug 2017	Intel SGX or AMD SEV-SNP TEEs	MIT License	packages provided	no (compiled by CMake or GNU Make)	build by GNU make build	run GNU make run
SPDM Tools	proof of concept for Linux and Windows (mingw)	Active since Nov 2023	TEE	Apache 2.0 or MIT	Medium complexity - all compilers and tools must be installed	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant
Certifier Framework For Confidential Computing	beta (version 0.1.1 from Aug 30, 2022)	active (3 commits in May 2024, over 1,000 commits in last 20 months)	Intel SGX platform; can also run on a simulated enclave for development and testing	Apache 2.0	medium (requires installation of standard Ubuntu packages but not additional sw; requires C++ build and following a detailed list of steps)	Yes, app needs to include artifacts necessary for certification	binary, with additional artifacts in files	standard run as a binary, with additional certification-related parameters
COCONUT-SVSM	in development, no stable	active (dense commit activity in the last 3 months,	AMD EPYC Generation 3 or newer	MIT	complex - building multiple complex	not applicable; as for guest OS, can be both	not applicable	not applicable

Project	Maturity	Development	Requirement	Licence	Installation	App adaptation	App deployment	App execution
	version released	over 1,500 commits since Mar 2023)	processor, SEV-SNP enabled in the BIOS settings, Linux host and guest kernels, EDK2 with SVSM support		components(QE MU, firmware, image) with SVSM and IGVM support, then building the sw itself	without and with SVSM support		
Enarx	mature, stable versions for Windows, macOS, Linux	medium (approx 1 commit a month in the last 6 months, with 2,500 commits since Sep 2019)	Intel SGX or AMD SEV-SNP TEEs; has the ability to run without these for development purposes	Apache 2.0	easy - packages provided; installation from source possible, detailed instructions are provided	yes, needs to be compiled in WebAssembly	via publishing into a repository	deployment of a published app from repository